

Discursive Pattern Changes of the Iranian Opposition during the 'Woman Life Freedom' protests (2022-2024)

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The 'Woman, Life, Freedom' protests mark the most significant critical juncture in contemporary Iranian political history. Despite months of nationwide protests and strong initial backing for forming an opposition coalition, the movement splintered with severe fragmentation. This thesis examines the puzzle of the failed consolidation of a political coalition and the resulting fragmentation, with a focus on the discursive institution of oppositionality. Using Critical Discourse Analysis, Discursive Pattern Analysis, and Episodic Discursive Analysis, this research deconstructs the evolving discourse among opposition groups. The study identifies the transition of discursive patterns from solidarity to hostility, attributed to the frame alignment strategies of the legacy opposition and the resultant hostile discourse from in-group consolidation efforts. The findings reveal that opposition groups' strategic maneuvers to hegemonize the WLF narrative contributed to increased fragmentation, challenging the movement's potential for unified consolidation. This thesis provides a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics shaping Iran's political opposition, offering insights for future scholarly exploration and practical implications for opposition movements globally.

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1. Exordium

September 2022 marks the most significant critical juncture in the contemporary history of Iranian politics. Many Iranians responded to the death of Mahsa Jina Amini under the custody of the Islamic Republic (IR) morality police with demands for regime change and overthrow of the IR.¹ People from every province took to the streets to voice their dissent for the ruling elite, and the subsequent events amalgamated to the longest ongoing protest movement in the country since the 1979 Islamic Revolution.²

The scale of the protests was not limited to Iran. Communities of Iranians in diaspora and the exiled opposition groups organized a number of international solidarity protests and marches across European capitals, Oceania and a number of cities in Northern America.³ Cumulatively, over a million Iranians partook in the demonstrations abroad. While the reported numbers within Iran remain contested, Human Rights Organization report the participation's scale throughout the protest period in the similar range. Those that didn't partake in the protests in fear of the crackdown, showed their discontent against the government through boycott of products and services closely affiliated with the government, and most notably the parliamentary elections of 2024.⁵

Surveys by the GAMAAN Institute manifest this demand in a sequence of empirical studies. The 2022 polls indicate that 80.9% of Iranians oppose the IR, up from 71% in 2019.⁶ In the 2024 polling, following the failure of the opposition and the regime change aspiration, the number was reported at 74.6%.⁷ The 2022 study suggested a plurality in preferences of Iranians for the establishment of an alternative government, with the presidential republic, constitutional monarchy, and parliamentary republic having respectively 28.5%, 22.3%, and 12% support from Iranians in Iran and 32%, 25.1% and 29% support from Iranians outside of Iran.⁸ Participants of the same poll inside Iran showed overwhelmingly optimistic views of the protests, with 67.3% believing it will succeed in toppling the government.⁹

¹ BBC Persian. "Mahsa Amini in Coma; Police Say She 'Suddenly Suffered Heart Complications'." *BBC Persian*, September 15, 2022. <https://www.bbc.com/persian/articles/c13jgpgznx5o>.

² Holly Dages, "Regime Change in Iran? Women, Life, Freedom," Atlantic Council, December 6, 2022, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/iransource/regime-change-iran-women-life-freedom/>.

³ CBC News, "Toronto Protesters Call for Solidarity with Iran After Mahsa Amini's Death," CBC News, October 8, 2022, <https://www.cbc.ca/news/canada/toronto/toronto-iran-solidarity-protest-1.6611322>.

⁴ Roshanak Astaraki, "Iranian Diaspora in Los Angeles Unites to Aid Anti-Government Protesters," VOA News, June 15, 2023, <https://www.voanews.com/a/iranian-diaspora-in-los-angeles-unites-to-aid-anti-government-protesters/7143904.html>.

⁵ Vivian Yee, "Iran Elections See Widespread Boycott Amid Calls for Change," *The New York Times*, March 1, 2024, <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/03/01/world/middleeast/iran-elections-boycott.html>.

⁶ GAMAAN. "Iran's Political Systems Survey: 2022." GAMAAN, 2022. <https://gamaan.org/>.

⁷ Maleki, Ammar. "Iranians' Attitudes Toward the 2024 Legislative Elections." GAMAAN, February 2024. <https://gamaan.org/>.

⁸ GAMAAN "Iran's Political Systems Survey: 2022.", 2022

⁹ Ibid.

Despite the popular demand of the public for a change, more than a year of civil disobedience, and continued local resistance, the opposition groups have failed to create a united front to consolidate the movement. What has been a puzzling observation, is the further fragmentation of the opposition after a failed attempt at creating a Coalition Council in February.¹⁰ This thesis is centered on this puzzle.

From a personal observation that prompted this research, the fragmentation is grave to such a scale that the opposition groups are more engaged in hostile antagonism of one another, gatekeeping oppositionality, and utilizing the social sorting mentality of social media as their space of strategizing their aspirations of regime change. It is through this observed dialogic failures that the opposition has lost its touch with the grassroots support in Iran and has been engaged in trivial conflicts that emerged in the aftermath of Coalition Council falling out.

The significance of examining this topic is anchored in three fundamental aspects:

1. **Assessment of Opposition Strength:** The vitality of an opposition movement is a critical barometer for gauging the autonomy of the incumbent government, influencing its domestic and international actions. Analyzing the strength of an opposition provides insight into the potential challenges and constraints faced by the ruling regime.
2. **Political Application of Discourse Analysis:** The phenomenon of a fragmented opposition struggling in its discourse extends beyond the Iranian context. Understanding the dynamics of discourse within opposition movements, especially after pivotal moments, can shed light on the opposition's behavior and the likely trajectory of the movement it supports. This knowledge forms a conceptual framework that can be applied to various global settings, offering a comparative perspective on opposition movements and their impact on governmental stability.
3. **Significance of the Woman Life Freedom (WLF) movement:** The WLF movement represents a crucial turning point that may have lasting effects on the structure of the IR and its opposition. Yet, the academic exploration of these protests and their implications for both the regime and its challengers remains limited, highlighting the need for thorough scholarly analysis.

The central research question this study aims to address is: What are the discursive patterns of opposition fragmentation, and how do they emerge? To tackle this question, the research outlines five key concepts through a literature review, forming the theoretical basis for subsequent empirical

¹⁰ Razavi, Sahar. "Discord in the Diaspora: Agonism in the Woman, Life, Freedom Movement for Democracy." *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 55, no. 4 (2023): 754–58. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020743823001435>.

investigation. A mixed-methods approach, blending qualitative and quantitative analyses, is proposed to comprehensively dissect the phenomenon.

The concepts explored in the subsequent chapter will begin with defining a paradigm of oppositionality, whereby it is interpreted as an institution shaped by the discourse of the actors within it. The literature will further explore how critical junctures and subsequent events shape a discourse, the strategies implemented by the opposition to maintain their role, and how the Iranian opposition shaped this discursive institution prior to the WLF protests.

The empirical section of the research will delineate the discourse frameworks, juxtaposing theoretical expectations against contemporary observations. The concluding chapter offers insights that could serve dual purposes: as a strategy guide for incumbent governments to suppress dissent or as a roadmap for opposition movements to refine their discourse strategies, fostering more effective change.

2. Discursive Institution of Oppositionality

Discursive institutionalism serves as a overarching framework within political science, recognizing the essential role of discourse in the transmission and exchange of ideas that ultimately shape institutions. V.Schmidt describes that discursive institutionalism extends beyond mere communication of ideas, individuals, collectives and history – emphasizing the importance of the discursive milieu that facilitates institutions.¹¹

According to V.Schmidt, institutions under this paradigm are perceived as both constraints and enablers of meaning, crafted and perpetuated by agents endowed with the capacity for expression, thought and speech.¹² These agents' "background ideational abilities" are instrumental in the formation and sustenance of institutions, while their "foreground discursive abilities"¹³ allow for the critical examination and potential modification of these institutions.

Schmidt further clarifies the dynamics of collective action within political entities, attributing its genesis to discourse patterns and structures. She simplifies this interaction by asserting, "We don't, after all, know what people are thinking or why they act the way they do until they say it. And we don't for the most part engage in collective action or in collective (re)thinking of our actions without the articulation, discussion, deliberation, and legitimization of our ideas about our actions."¹⁴ This perspective posits *discourse* as a linchpin in the exchange of ideas and the reevaluation of communal objectives that construct institutions.

The author argues that the cradle and construction of institutions are inextricably linked to the "foreground discursive abilities"¹⁵ of thinking and speaking agents. These abilities empower individuals to critically assess and potentially alter the institutions within which they operate, following a logic of communication. Such abilities enforce institutional change, as they encapsulate the capacity of individuals to conceptualize beyond the constraints of existing institutions.¹⁶ This includes critically discussing these frameworks, engaging in deliberation, persuading both oneself and others to reassess their perspectives on these institutions, and ultimately taking decisive action towards modification. The concept extends to the formation of "discursive coalitions" within revolutionary processes, which are essential for challenging the entrenched interests of the in-charge polity.

¹¹Vivien A. Schmidt, "Taking Ideas and Discourse Seriously: Explaining Change through Discursive Institutionalism as the Fourth 'New Institutionalism'," *European Political Science Review* 2, no. 1 (2010): 1–25,

¹² *Ibid.* p.2

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.* p.4

¹⁵ *Ibid.* p.1

¹⁶ *Ibid.* p.6

Similarly, in the communicative political sphere, these abilities play the central role in informing and galvanizing the public opinion. This discourse-based interpretation underscores the dynamic nature of institutional evolution – positing a change in the discursive patterns corroborates with a change in a revolutionary process.

A revolution, in this work, is conceptualized as the process within the *Institution of the Opposition*. We observe how sentient actors, engrossed in oppositionality, leverage discourse to sculpt the definition of oppositionality and the contours of what constitutes the WLF. The discourse facilitates a shared understanding and alignment among the opposition members, being either a deliberation for a democratic structure, or what in the Iranian case has been colloquially called a *meat-grinder*.

"Revolutionary action is shaped by revolutionary discourse"¹⁷ Moaddel posits in his study of the 1979 Islamic Revolution. He distinguishes revolutionary discourse from ordinary political discourse by its foundational aim to negate existing power structures and the conventional mechanisms of opposition. This form of discourse emerges as a radical departure from previous modes of social action, introducing an unprecedented practical and ideological approach to social change.

According to Moaddel, the essence of a revolutionary situation transcends to dual sovereignty; it embodies a clash between two ideologically antagonistic universes: that of the state and the opposition.¹⁸ WLF fits the definition of the state of exception and an emergent revolutionary discourse. As is the case with such critical junctures, we are given the opportunity to examine the dynamics of oppositionality and sovereignty through the discursive construction of the revolutionary institution of 'Woman Life Freedom.' To this end, the subsequent chapter focus on exploring how critical juncture invokes a discursive turn in political ethos of a collective, and to what extent this turn is reverberated in the institution of the oppositionality.

¹⁷ Mansoor Moaddel, Mansoor Moaddel, "Ideology as Episodic Discourse: The Case of the Iranian Revolution," in *Social Movements*, ed. Stanford M. Lyman (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 1995). p.250

¹⁸ Ibid.

2.1. Discursive Junctures

In "Discursive Turns and Critical Junctures" (2020), D. della Porta et al. address the dynamics of discourse evolution during critical junctures, examining how discursive actors recalibrate their narratives in response to transformative events. The authors identify events such as the Charlie Hebdo attacks as catalysts capable of challenging prevailing interpretations and instigating pivotal changes in public debates across various interconnected issues. Such incidents precipitate a polarization of viewpoints and also lead to a newfound consensus through public controversies and discursive engagements.¹⁹

The WLF, triggered by Mahsa Amini's hospitalization and death, exemplifies the type of critical juncture the authors describe. This event catalyzed a communicative arena teeming with diverse actors, including journalists, exiled politicians, athletes, human rights societies and a breed of oppositionality produced under the pressure of security forces in social media – the Anonymous influencers. All these opposition stratas advocating a position against the incumbent regime, while engaging in intra-opposition discursive conflicts.

The authors contend that in the aftermath of violent events, civil society organizations participate within the mass-media public sphere and also forge their own communicative spaces.²⁰ This phenomenon resonates with the earlier conceptualized *Discursive Institution of Oppositionality* wherein civil societies partly embrace and modify official narratives, while also crafting alternative framings to stimulate debate in distinct public spheres. The strategic use of discursive framing as a tool for consolidating oppositionality is explored further in Chapter 2.3, necessitating a dedicated conceptual framework due to its complexity.

The concept of "eventful temporality"²¹ within the ambit of social movements posits that such movements possess the inherent potential to not merely adapt to existing structures but to fundamentally alter them. Eventful protests are interpreted as instances of heightened agency and transformative relational dynamics, setting apart extraordinary periods of intense activity from the quiescence of normal times. Protest events and acts of political violence can serve as punctuating catalysts of disrupting the discursive equilibria, and propelling accelerated and often unintended changes.²²

¹⁹ Donatella della Porta et al., "Discursive Turns and Critical Junctures: An Introduction," in *Discursive Turns and Critical Junctures: Debating Citizenship after the Charlie Hebdo Attacks*, Oxford Studies in Culture and Politics (New York, 2020; online edn, Oxford Academic, 18 June 2020),

²⁰ Ibid. p.5

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid. p.5-14

Building on this framework, the discussion extends to the dynamics of time and protest events. Authors make a reference to Beissingers argument, positing during periods when time seems to condense, the proliferation of protest events ignites further contentious episodes, embedding them within a "punctuated history of heightened challenges and relative stability."²³ This cyclical pattern of events and reactions reshapes relationships, embedding them within narratives of struggle, altering expectations for future contestations, influencing the conduct of the forces maintaining the status quo, and ultimately redefining the semantic landscape and the discursive institution of oppositionality.

The nature of critical junctures is inherently rooted in existing structures, while they are simultaneously characterized by their openness to unpredictable shifts. Contrary to being strictly determined by pre-existing frameworks, critical junctures offer opportunities for divergence, propelled by contingent events. These events are crucial in the evolution of the juncture, as the varied decision making and responses of actors to emerging challenges poses the potential to redefine relationships and the identity of the movement.²⁴

The literature further theorizes that a critical juncture, if it catalyzes systemic transformation, initiates a domino effect. This transformative sequence, once it is recognized and named, furnishes future actors with a reference point — serving as a signal, model, or aspiration and a threat the existing discursive institution of oppositionality. Consequently, the progression of such a juncture becomes path-dependent, influenced by the continuity of its narrative until it encounters new disruptive events that might alter its course.²⁵

Applying this framework to the WLF movement, it is observed that the its emergence as a revolutionary process within a specific discursive frame and as an institution of oppositionality **presented a challenge not only to the incumbent government but also to the pre-existing agencies within the opposition.**

This begs a hypothesis that traditional opposition factions may have a strategic inclination towards preserving the status quo, especially if the discursive narrative championed by the WLF movement threatens to destabilize the established discursive institution of oppositionality. Substracting the discursive approach, the history of political mobilizations and revolutionary movements is rich with this precedent.

²³ Ibid. p.5

²⁴ Ibid. p.25

²⁵ Ibid. p.106

During the The Russian Civil War (1917-1923) various anti-Bolshevik forces, including the White Armies, nationalist movements, and others, were often in conflict with each other over their goals and territories. However, they sometimes cooperated against the Bolsheviks (Red Army), seeing them as a greater existential threat to their causes. More recently, during rise of ISIS in Syria and Iraq (2013-2018) various factions in the Syrian Civil War, including some opposition rebel groups and the Syrian government led by Bashar al-Assad, found themselves at odds with the Islamic State – leading to complex and sometimes shifting alliances, with even international coalitions forming that included countries with opposing interests in the region, all aiming to defeat ISIS.

This is not to suggest any form of alignment between WLF movement and two aforementioned political movements – but rather the effect WLF movement has generated through disrupting what constitutes *the Opposition*. **It created an impression of alignment between the IR and the traditional opposition movement hesitant of a radical change in its alleged determination to oust the IR and establish a democratic regime.** This also needs to be addressed that what WLF movement has generated or how it is ontologically defined, is contested. This contestability will be further addressed in the subsequent chapters.

Inferring from Porta et.al. 's argument, controlling the movement's discursive narrative from its cradle becomes a matter of existential importance for the existing opposition, as it determines their relevance and influence within the evolving and emerging political landscape.²⁶ It is posited that critical junctures often catalyze polarizing debates over the optimal responses to crises. Yet, within the framework of deliberative democracy, consensus—understood as mutual comprehension—is esteemed as a hallmark of deliberative processes and an alternative to control or hegemonize the discursive narrative of a movement. Here, decisions are made through convincing dialogue, where the exchange of compelling reasons leads to acceptable decisions.

It is inherent in critical junctures to precipitate stark conflicts and a polarization of viewpoints.²⁷ With the onset of a critical juncture in political discourse, traditional actors of the institution of opposition face an ultimatum: adapt or perish. This adaptation, however, unfolds with bifurcating into two divergent paths: The pursuit of consensus through cooperation or the competitive hegemonization of the discursive frame. This dichotomy encapsulates the essence of the discursive behaviour within opposition factions. Such behaviour manifests through what we can conceptualize as *episodic junctures* — pivotal moments that follow the initial eruption of a critical juncture, during which actors weigh their responses in light of the evolving discursive change.

²⁶ Ibid. p.4

²⁷ Ibid. p.48

Episodic junctures are, in essence, the consequential events that ripple out from the epicenter of a critical juncture, each carrying the potential to either consolidate the emerging discourse or to further complicate the narrative terrain. Understanding the discursive patterns of the WLF protests necessitates the individual examination of these episodic junctures. These episodes can be characterized as aftershocks and formative events that provide the canvas upon which actors sketch their strategic discursive patterns or lack thereof – which is observed in the opposition’s current state of failure. These episodic junctures represent the points of recalibration, where the dynamics of discourse are reassessed, and new strategies are formulated in response to the unfolding narratives.

This process involves mapping the trajectory of discourse from initial disruption through subsequent episodic junctures, identifying patterns of convergence (towards consensus) or divergence (towards hegemonization). Analyzing the content, tone, and direction of discourse among opposition groups reveals the underlying strategies, whether they aim for cooperative collective action or for competitive hegemonization.

Given the centrality of episodic junctures in the evolution of discursive patterns during a revolution, several questions emerge as crucial for analysis: In what ways do these discursive shifts contribute to the reconstitution or transformation of oppositionality? What factors influence the decision-making process of these actors as they navigate episodic junctures?

A dated, albeit foundational, piece of literature that offers a pivotal examination of how episodic shifts in discourse influence the very essence of revolution and the formation of oppositional institutions will be explored in the next chapter, as we return to Moaddel's *Ideology as Episodic Discourse: The Case of the Iranian Revolution*. (1992)

2.2. Discursive Episodes

Moaddel's analysis of the 1979 Islamic Revolution marks a pivotal departure from traditional Marxist and Interpretive theoretical frameworks, addressing their limitations in accounting for the complex dynamics leading to the formation of the IR. He introduces an empirical methodology that emphasizes the role of discursive developments within ideological shifts, delineating the revolution's evolution in three distinct phases: pre-revolution, during the revolution, and post-revolution. Moaddel's method focuses on the imageries and symbolism inherent in Shi'i Islam reveals how these elements were instrumental in both initiating and sustaining the revolution, thus forming what we've conceptualized as the Institution of Oppositionality.

To weave ideology into the narrative of the revolution's causes and processes, Moaddel draws a crucial analytical distinction. He differentiates between the revolution as *content*—defined by specific institutional transformations within a concise timeframe—and the revolution as a *mode* of historical action, inherently shaped by revolutionary ideology.

According to Moaddel, it is the pervasiveness of ideology that transcends routine political disputes and social differences among participants, fostering a unified communitarian relationship directed against the state. This ideological underpinning serves to distinguish revolution from mere power struggles, emphasizing that what Moaddel identifies as ideology comprises the discursive patterns that rally around certain ideals of a movement.

Moaddel explores the centrality of Shi'ism as the ideological epicenter and foundational structure of the discursive institution of oppositionality during the 1979 Iranian Revolution. He unpacks the belief system rooted in the Imamate— a lineage of charismatic leaders deemed the rightful guides post-Prophet Mohammad. The notion that the Twelfth Imam's occultation leaves no legitimate earthly authority underscores a profound ideological conviction within Twelver Shi'ism, challenging the legitimacy of all temporal rulers and positioning Shi'ism as a critical oppositional force in Iranian politics.

Expanding on the concept of “*Ideology*”, Moaddel argues that it transcends mere ideational constructs or textual manifestations. Ideology, he posits, is discernible in the strategic actions of individuals and the tangible outputs of its proponents. Ideology, thus conceptualized, is a *dynamic discursive pattern that constructs the broader architecture of oppositionality*. It intertwines discursive practices with non-discursive actions, shaping the framework within which actors negotiate their strategic interventions. Ideology emerges as a discourse encompassing principles, symbols, and rituals that

actors deploy to navigate specific historical challenges. This discursive approach facilitates the construction of action strategies and determines the boundaries of permissible coalitions and the landscape of intellectual justifications for actions, ultimately influencing the course of historical episodes and the nature of oppositional movements.

While the WLF lacks the monolithic structure that is prerequisite in understand what *ideology* it professes, through analysis of its entangled discursive patterns one can hypothesize a close contour of what ideology it could embody.

To this end, we may conceptualize the interplay of discourse and revolution as codependent and co-constitutive. In between the two axes, the institution of oppositionality, comprised of actors and stakeholders within the opposition, is constructed and deconstructed through discursive episodes and discursive actions — all of which coalesce back to the shaping the next sequence of the critical juncture as a revolutionary process. This coproductionist narrative is revisited in the methodology section to contrive a method of empirically exploring the entanglement between discourse, oppositionality and revolution.

Complementary to Porta et.al., Moaddel posits that the construction, sustenance, and hegemony of a specific discursive narrative must be contextualized within its unique episodic framework. He approaches macrostructural transformations as a series of discrete episodes, each acting as a critical link in a chain of historically significant occurrences. These episodes are distinguished not only by their interrelations but also by their distinctions from preceding and subsequent events, echoing Porta's conception of sequential critical junctures. Throughout the following sections of this research, we adopt this concept as "*Discursive Episodes*".

Moaddel argues that such events possess the capacity to alter the worldviews of ideological creators, thereby influencing the predominance of certain discourses within society. Consequently, he conceptualizes ideology as *inherently episodic in nature*.

'Discourse' for Moaddel is an interactive argument or exchange between two entities, often reflecting opposing perspectives or ideologies. In the context of a revolution —which fits the defining characteristics of the a *state of exception*— revolutionary discourse stands in stark contrast to the prevailing discourse of the state. It proposes an alternative framework for understanding and addressing the challenges of social existence, a vision achievable solely through the direct, unmediated actions of the masses mobilized by revolutionary fervor.

Through his analysis of the 1979 revolution, he demonstrates how a revolutionary discursive field systematically compresses the state's discursive space, effectively constraining its operational freedom. Within this process, ideology emerges as the dominant architecture of human action according to its inherent logic and dynamics. This ideological ascendancy reconfigures individual subjectivities among the revolution's adherents, aligning personal sacrifices and even the prospect of death with the overarching narrative and objectives defined by the episodic discourse of the revolution. He necessitates the emergence of a hegemonic discourse is bound to the episodic discourses that construct the ideology of the revolutionary frame.

Khomeini's vision of the Guardianship of the Jurist represented merely one facet of the broader Islamic oppositional discourse, which as Moaddel argues, was itself shaped through a dialectical process of engagement with the state's narrative.

The creation and evolution of the revolutionary Islamic discourse, as Moaddel notes, were significantly shaped by the dialectical exchanges between state and opposition forces. This reflects a Marxist dialectical approach, wherein discourse is seen as evolving from the clash of opposing ideologies, leading to a synthesis that shapes societal structures. Moaddel's analysis notably underrepresents the complexity of intra-oppositional discourse and its role in the emergence of Khomeini's discourse as the dominant narrative. This gap in Moaddel's work overlooks the nuanced dialogues and power struggles within the opposition, which were critical in consolidating Khomeini's ideological hegemony over other competing narratives within the revolutionary movement.

He attributes the ascendancy of Khomeini's ideological framework to a series of catalytic events, notably the backlash against the Shah's polity following the publication of an article slandering Khomeini as a foreign agent in 1978. This moment, marked by violent clashes in Qom, signifies the critical juncture that set the revolution's trajectory. What followed from hereon, according to Moaddel, is a rapid pacification of the other opposition groups with overly reductivist and descriptive explanation. A critical oversight in Moaddel's study is this scant attention to the dialogues and strategic considerations within the opposition that facilitated Khomeini's rise to ideological preeminence. This oversight simplifies the complex interplay of ideas, strategies, and power dynamics that characterized the revolutionary discourse and reduces it to a binary confrontation between state and a monolithic opposition.

Furthermore, Moaddel's characterization of the pluralist opposition's acquiescence to Khomeini's ideological vision underpins a broader critique. It suggests a reductive understanding of the opposition's motivations and the strategic misreadings of Khomeini's agenda. He argues the Tudeh

party and other groups in the Left accepted Khomeini's hegemony, because "*they believed that he was a revolutionary democrat or petty bourgeois anti-imperialist and overlooked the fact that he was equally anti-Communist.*"²⁸ Likewise with the liberals, he argues they didn't contemplate the inconsistency of their democratic ideals with Khomeini's revolutionary Islam and the Guardianship of the Jurist.²⁹

Moaddel also observes that "highly educated women, who had proudly worn the veil for the sake of the Revolution, probably had no idea what Khomeini and his followers would do to women's liberty in the post-revolutionary period."³⁰ The veil, once a unifying symbol of resistance against the Shah's regime, has remarkably re-emerged as a focal point of contention in the WLF protests. Those who donned the veil, scarcely foresaw the implications of Shiism discourse on women's liberties as the catalyst for the emergence of another critical juncture – the killing of Mahsa Amini in the hands of those enforcing Shiism. While the veil has emerged to the spotlight of framing the WLF protests, it defracts to a spectrum of colours and meanings for different actors within the current opposition.

Just as the discursive acts of the Pahlavi monarchy inadvertently shaped the opposition that led to its overthrow, the IR's gender apartheid has centralised womanhood within the current framework of oppositionality. The *womanhood* and *veil* as a continuum symbolic struggle are but one of the episodic discourses that emerged during the last two years. Along with women, religious and ethnic minorities, namely Kurds and Baloch, have been subjected to the most aggressive scale of crackdown during nationwide protests. The fact that the Iranian peripheries are subjected to more brutal crackdown is not an isolated incident. It is a long-observed predictable mechanism of authoritarian states that regions in the peripheries are subjected to more aggressive political violence than those closer to the pivots of power. Another emergent frame, ergo, most consolidated in the peripheries, has been centered on the rights of non-Persian and non-Shia communities.

The coalesce of multiplicity of discursive frames, shaped by episodic discourses of those within the institution of oppositionality, bifurcates into two paths that were mentioned in the previous section. The frames will either merge in deliberation of collective action, or attempt to hegemonize the discursive field.

²⁸ CITE

²⁹ CITE

³⁰ CITE

2.3. Discursive Frames

When discursive actors construct a point of view with the intention to project a particular interpretation of a given situation, they are engaged in what scholars in social studies define as framing. J. Kuypers (2009) identifies four ways through which framing takes place: actors define a problem, diagnose the problem, make a moral judgment, and suggest remedies.³¹

Given the fragmented state of the opposition, it can be theorized that the current state is attributed to the divergence in the framing of opposition groups. Each group posits its ideological narrative as the remedy and defines the problem in a particularly reductive manner that amplifies the importance of the particular group's remedies. According to Kuypers, frames form the central idea behind a movement.³²

During movements that entail political mobilization, actors adopt the projection of their frames in congruence with the emerging discourse to resonate with a broader audience. This phenomenon was identified by D.Snow and R.Benford (2000) as “Frame Alignment.”³³ The authors define four strategies of frame alignment: bridging, amplification, extension, and transformation.

Frame bridging involves linking a movement to an unmobilized cluster of people who share similar views but lack any organization for mobilization.³⁴ Frame amplification involves invigorating a problem to galvanize a larger support base.³⁵ Frame extension entails extending the ontological boundaries and ethos of a defined movement to encompass the views and sentiments of an emerging movement.³⁶ Lastly, frame transformation is adopted when the existing frame is either antithetical to the emerging movement or lacks the resonance to appear relevant.³⁷ During frame transformation, how the actors navigate a new discursive terrain may or may not be burdened by their former position. This uncertainty, the authors argue, lessens the preference for frame transformation by discursive actors.

Frame alignment strategies become more evident around the critical juncture and, as discussed in the preceding chapter, the subsequent discursive episodes. The illustration in Figure 1.0 provides a visual conceptualization of this alignment. The large circle denotes the Discursive Institutions of Opposition. The white marker in the center represents the discursive juncture caused by a critical juncture. The black spots around the marker are the discursive episodes following the juncture. The fluid shapes

³¹ Kuypers, Jim A. “Framing Analysis from a Rhetorical Perspective,” *Doing News Framing Analysis*. Paul D’Angelo and Jim A. Kuypers, eds. (New York: Routledge, 2010), 286-311.

³² *Ibid.* p.288

³³ Benford, Robert D., and David A. Snow. “Framing Processes and Social Movements: An Overview and Assessment.” *Annual Review of Sociology* 26 (2000): 611–39. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/223459>.

³⁴ *Ibid.* p.623

³⁵ *Ibid.* p.624

³⁶ *Ibid.* p.625

³⁷ *Ibid.*

around the sequential events and the discursive juncture are discursive frames by the actors of the opposition. While all frames revolve around the critical juncture, they do not adhere to the same shape or narrative. The frames are formed tacitly around selective discursive episodes with the objective of aligning with the central critical juncture. While the juncture and the episodes are temporally relevant, the frames, as ideological narratives, are consciously created by the opposition actors in the deliberation of hegemonization or public mobilization.

Another interpretation of frame alignment has been presented by M. Steinberg's *Tilting the Frame: Considerations on Collective Action Framing from a Discursive Turn* (1998). Contrary to the traditional frame analysts' depiction of discursive frames as relatively stable systems of meaning, Steinberg posits a more fluid conceptualization.³⁸ He argues that frames should be understood as being crafted from the tactics and strategies employed by collective actors, alongside what these actors present as in empirical discourse.³⁹ He illustrates how frames are actively constructed and reconstructed through the discursive practices of collective action by anchoring his argument with references to empirical studies, including Jenness's examination of framing processes within anti-violence activism in the lesbian and gay community, Benford's work on anti-nuclear activism, and Capek's analysis of the environmental justice frame.⁴⁰

Following Goffman's thesis on dynamics of frames, Steinberg engages with framing theory as a process of representation – it changes, overlaps and merges with other frames to represent a larger or a more consolidated group of adherents. He points out that undrestnading the frame opens a paradigm

³⁸ Marc W. Steinberg, *Tilting the Frame: Considerations on Collective Action Framing from a Discursive Turn* (Springer, 1998)

³⁹ *Ibid.* 855

⁴⁰ *Ibid.* 848

into the ideological underpinnings that structure opposition, mobilize participants, and maintain the cohesion vital for the success of collective actions.⁴¹

Frames in this term are shaped around selective episodic disruptions –discursive episodes– and play a critical role in the manifestation of collective action. They reveal ideological visions as inherently contested and dynamic, with discourse serving as a direct conduit of meanings within frames, thus signifying the overarching ideology that guides its development.

Steinberg also introduces the concept of "Consensus mobilization" as a key mechanism through which frames evolve, diminish, or coalesce. Consensus mobilization begins with frame alignment and the demonstration of a discursive repertoire's relevance in identifying problems, offering critiques, and suggesting solutions. He posits that the stability of a discursive repertoire—and, by extension, the frames it supports—may fluctuate with the social movement's scale, duration, and the density of connections within its multiorganizational field. An example of this observed during the WLF protest is the compatibility observed in frames of national liberation and woman emancipation. The initial coalition building projects which we will explore in the empirical section were built through frame alignment and consensus mobilization.⁴²

Steinberg draws a relational map between consensus mobilization and misrecognition of heterogeneity as unity during a critical juncture to describe how a popular movement fragments after the onset of the discursive juncture that enables a strong theory construction for the discursive pattern changes during the protest movements.⁴³ In its early stages, the movement's ability to mobilize diverse groups was enhanced by the multivocality of discourse, allowing for the coexistence of multiple and sometimes divergent meanings within a shared discursive repertoire. This multiplicity of voices within the discursive field enabled a form of misrecognition, where heterogeneity was perceived as unity. As different groups with potentially divergent interests and identities utilized the same discursive repertoire, they articulated what they perceived as common claims and understandings.

Extrapolating this, the leadership of the movement can also find itself disconnected from the grassroots participants and foster an environment where the originally unified meanings within discursive repertoires might be subject to reinterpretation or distortion, thereby accelerating the decline of a frame's influence.⁴⁴ There are other key factors that determine the efficacy and longevity of a frame, identified by Steinberg. These include media processes, protest cycles, state interventions, elite

⁴¹ Ibid. p.857

⁴² Ibid. p.846

⁴³ Ibid. p.860

⁴⁴ Ibid. p.846

manipulations, and internal mechanisms that reinforce cohesion among social movement actors.⁴⁵ He adds when activists and social movement organizations adeptly align their frames with public perceptions of politics and social issues, these frames are more likely to resonate with their intended audiences.⁴⁶

One mechanism through which divergence accelerates, is embedded at the core of frame construction by every group – the dialogic transformation of identity. Steinberg posits the discourse within a frame navigates a terrain of group identity, where the delineation between "us" and "them" becomes susceptible to the appropriation of multiple voices and complicating the endeavor to demarcate and stabilize group boundaries. Such efforts at defining collective identity inadvertently magnify the dilemmas associated with establishing clear group delineations, as the endeavor to articulate a unified group voice may inadvertently suppress the plurality inherent within the movement.

Once again, we ought to inquire: How do the mechanisms of framing and identity politics contribute to the construction or deconstruction of the 'other' within the discursive institutions? How does the dialogue between 'us' and 'them' evolve in the context of heightened mobilization and contested identities? This line of inquiry naturally leads us to a deeper examination of discursive otherness explored in the next chapter.

⁴⁵ Ibid. p.850

⁴⁶ Ibid.

2.4. Othering Discourse

A study that will be revisited in the empirical section is A. Mohammadi and A. Mohammadi's *Post-Revolutionary Iranian Exiles: A Study in Impotence* (1987), which reads not as a diagnosis of the opposition after 1979, but rather a timeless prognosis of the Iranian opposition. The authors reflect to a political sectarian divide in the opposition by arguing "The exile groupings are, after all, in part the products of the Pahlavi era and suffer its same deformities of political culture: severe mistrust amongst participants, an intense egoistic jostling for leadership, and an individualism which constantly prevents any coalition of forces from lasting very long."⁴⁷ the authors discuss ideological rigidity within these groups: "Many groups also manifest an ideological rigidity which allows the 1 percent of disagreement to triumph over the 99 percent of shared views, thus preventing compromise or a more pragmatic, and therefore more effective, politics."⁴⁸

The authors note the opposition has fallen out with their domestic support due to their inability to communicate readily and directly without resorting to abstract rhetorics that are ambiguous hollow and undetermined. Each of the opposition groups have strategic disagreements over their course of action to begin a counter-revolution mobilization against the newly established the IR, and their leadership has resorted to rigid ideological framing that has no dialogic function outside securing its hegemony over the institution of the opposition. In the absence of strategic frame alignment, each group has identified itself through its ideological structures and objectives for a post-IR Iran. The "othering" device is not only applied to the government, but also to the opposition groups for the sake of establishing a more consolidated identity of "self".

Each set of actors within a frame can be studied as through the prisms of E. Said's *Orientalism* (1978), which approaches the critique of othering as strongly dualistic and two-dimensional.⁴⁹ Said explores the construction of the idea of the Orient from what is not the Occident. He argues the perception of the Occident as a familiar territory and superior power against the inferiority of the Orient justified the colonialist propogations and its subsequent outcomes.⁵⁰ This mode of othering involved a dialectical approach, where opposites like 'static/developing,' 'irrational/rational,' and 'barbaric/civilized' were employed to perpetuate the colonial discourse, reinforcing the narrative that favoured a particular institution. This dualistic antagonism in Iranian discourse of opposition has also been realized by a number of political activists who have attributed it to the manichean and moralistic national literatures

⁴⁷ Annabelle Sreberny-Mohammadi and Ali Mohammadi "Post-Revolutionary Iranian Exiles: A Study in Impotence" (Taylor & Francis, Ltd. 1987) p.118

⁴⁸ Ibid. p.126

⁴⁹ Edward W. Said, *Orientalism* (New York: Pantheon Books, 1978)

⁵⁰ Ibid.

that are built on a rigid contrast of light/dark and good/evil with a lack in accepting the nuanced grey areas in-between.

Such power dynamics explored through discourse extend to expressions, flags, and symbols as discursive acts that contribute to the definition of *self* among each of the opposition groups. R. Wodak, one of the central figures of Vienna School of Critical Discourse Analysis, defines discourse as a social practice embedded in different layers of context.⁵¹ Discourses both constitute and are constituted by these situational, institutional, and social contexts. They establish relationships between identities and knowledge, which is particularly relevant in studying the discursive constructions of group identity as a socially and context-dependent identity.⁵²

Critical Discourse Analysis allows us to deconstruct identities of the oppositionality and understand how each group perceived the identity of a *legitimate opposition*.⁵³ By utilizing Critical Discourse Analysis and acknowledging the role of *Othering* in shaping the agencies behind and within every discursive frame, we can demarcate the particular phrases and thematic discourses used by different groups for the construction of their discursive frames.

⁵¹ Ruth Wodak and Michael Meyer, eds., *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis*, 2nd ed. (London: SAGE Publications, 2009), <https://sk.sagepub.com/books/methods-of-critical-discourse-analysis>.

⁵²Ibid. p.38-43

⁵³Ibid. p.95

3. Methodology

This dissertation –with incorporation of adaptive and novel methods– is a follow up to Moaddel’s episodic discursive analysis of the 1979 revolution. It incorporates a wide range of methods to produce the first academic work on the Iranian institution of oppositionality following the WLF protests.

Studies centered on discourse typically rely on interpretative and qualitative methods – arguably coming short to empirically and objectively illustrate discursive junctures and subsequent episodes leading to shifts in the discursive frames. Each of the works explored in the preceding chapter introduced a new method of analyzing a political phenomenon through its discursive structures.

Porta et. al. largely used Critical Discourse Analysis, Moaddel introduces episodic discursive analysis, and Steinberg posits Frame analysis. All these methods have reliance on interpretive methods to semantically decipher discursive acts. Meanwhile, studies employing purely quantitative and statistical methods predominantly focus on semantic sentiment analysis and are poised with inherent inability to capture the nuanced and context-dependent nature of discourse. Quantitative methods can efficiently identify patterns and frequencies of certain words or phrases within a corpus of texts, they often fail to grasp the underlying meanings, intentions, and power dynamics that these words convey in specific contexts. Likewise, they can may produce a reductivist knowledge through oversimplification of complex discursive phenomena. The measurable elements of text overlook the complexities of discourse. Ergo, understanding the discursive pattern changes of a movement is best approached through a mixed method that applies the strengths of both approaches in a methodical roadmap.

Building on the premise that the WLF movement as a discursive juncture has altered the paradigms of oppositionality to the IR, and acknowledging its relevance as an ongoing movement, this research aims to construct the bedrock for future studies on Iranian political discourse and the subsequent discursive episodes.

To answer “What” are the discursive patterns, we must deconstruct patterns as recurring discursive themes and frames employed by opposition groups to challenge the status quo, mobilize support, and articulate their vision for maximized support from the public. To answer “How” discursive patterns of fragmentation emerge, we must recognize their absence in the nascent phases of the phenomenon under study. These two queries embody the central research question, which reads: What are the discursive patterns of opposition fragmentation, and how they emerge?

The emergence of discursive patterns is inherently linked to the co-constitution of *discursive acts* and their respective *actors*. Concurrently, alongside the identification of these actors, and assessing their frames at the onset of the movement, we undertake an examination of their discursive output and political expressions over a 72-week period (September 2022 - February 2024) to process the timeseries change of their discursive patterns.

The primary tool adopted for this research is Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), which encompasses a spectrum of qualitative research methods, including discourse analysis, symbolic analysis, semiotics, and ethnography. Discursive Pattern Analysis (DPA) is then employed to identify the key discursive episodes through the temporal evolution of discursive patterns. In this research, DPA is conducted within a defined timeframe, specifically from September 8th to January 15th, which is subdivided into 72 weeks. DPA encompasses five primary methods: Thematic Analysis, Discursive Tokenization, Discursive Frequency Analysis, Time-Series Analysis, and Comparative Analysis.

84 Telegram channels were selected based on a detailed selection method outlined in the subsequent section. Subsequently, all textual posts and discursive outputs from these channels spanning from September 8th to January 15th were scraped using publicly available OSINT tools and Telegram API. Then, the scraped content underwent Tokenization, which involved categorizing specific phrases into semantic codes, which were subsequently processed in the next stage as thematic components. Thematic coding analysis was then employed to systematically categorize the discursive content into distinct themes. In total, 43 distinct themes were created through this manual coding process. These themes were then organized into three overarching discursive patterns observed within the dataset.

Lastly, we employ the Temporal Token Frequency Analysis in this study to combine elements of Time-series analysis and Keyword Frequency analysis. Token frequency analysis was conducted for each dataset, enabling the determination of the distribution of tokens within the three overarching thematic structures identified in the study. Each discursive pattern was analyzed as a separate time series to understand its temporal behavior over the 72 weeks. This decomposition provided insights into the underlying patterns and cyclic behavior of each discourse type. Change point detection was also employed to identify significant shifts in the discursive patterns over time.

As the DPA helps us with identifying the date of the key discursive episode whence the shift happens, we employ Episodical Discursive Analysis (EDA) to adequately examine these events – or 'phenomena' – with extensive contextual detail. EDA recognizes discursive acts and actors as mutually constitutive forces behind discursive episodes.

4. Framing The Revolution

The first theory proposes legacy opposition groups aligned their discursive frames –exclusionary dialogic institutions– as the legitimize opposition discourse. This is followed by another assumption, that this decision lead to competitive frame expansion that hampered dialogical consensus-building discourse.

The deconstruction of this theory and its examination requires three stages. First, delineating what is the discursive frame of the WLF movement and its ideological manifestations. Second, what are the discursive frames of the opposition. Third, inferring how the opposition framing strategies contributed to competitive frame alignment.

A significant aspect covered in the literature review is the notion of discursive frames and the strategies inherent in the framing process. The initial objective of this chapter is to construct a more objective framework of the protest movement by considering the demographics of the participants, the slogans utilized, and the various discursive acts executed nationwide in support of the protests.

Subsequently, the chapter aims to elucidate the evolution of the protest's semantic transformation and the significance of slogans as discursive streams, which adapt in accordance with the progression of the movement and the episodes it encounters. Building on this objective framework, the analysis will then scrutinize the frames advanced by different actors involved in the protests. This examination draws upon Steinberg's thesis, suggesting that politically motivated organizations strive for frame expansion and alignment by projecting their discursive frames onto the movement as a whole. This chapter employs CDA to dissect the language and frames crafted by these groups. This analysis predominantly focuses on the use of slogans and populist acts designed to rally and expand support.

4.1. Demographic Framing

The significant involvement of women in the 2022 protests is manifest in the demographic makeup of the fatalities, the nature of the discursive acts, and the slogans voiced by the demonstrators. The catalyst for this widespread movement was the death of Mahsa Amini, following an encounter with the morality police over an alleged violation of the IR's mandatory hijab laws, thrusting women's rights and freedoms to the forefront of the protests. The initial demonstrations erupted in Tehran, outside Kasra hospital, immediately following the announcement of Mahsa's hospitalization.⁵⁴ Her subsequent death galvanized the protests, intensifying their scale and spreading them across various major cities throughout Iran.⁵⁵ In Saqqez, Mahsa's hometown, the act of women removing their headscarves during her funeral while chanting "Jin, Jian, Azadi" (Woman, Life, Freedom in Kurdish) became a powerful symbol of resistance, with the slogan quickly gaining traction and echoing across the country.^{56,57}

This act of defiance and the slogan's proliferation across Iran mirrored the earlier 2017 protests, notably the 'Girl of Enghelab Street' incident,⁵⁸ where Iranian women publicly burned their mandatory hijabs and displayed them on sticks like flags in protest to the compulsory veiling and the gender apartheid institution set by the IR.

The WLF movement saw a significant number of arrests, with reported figures varying: Voice of America stated over 60,000 Iranians were detained⁵⁹, while official the IR sources cited 22,000.⁶⁰ The injured count, particularly from Kurdish provinces, was estimated by human rights groups at around 8,000.⁶¹ Notably, 109 individuals face the threat of execution.⁶² Information leaked by the Blackreward hack group from an IRGC bulletin revealed a tragic death toll of over 1,500 during the protests, including 71 minors.⁶³

The protests prominently featured the youth, as indicated by an IRGC-affiliated newspaper report and subsequent acknowledgments by high-ranking officials including Hossein Salami and Mohammad Hossein Bagheri who commented "our student organizations should not become politicized, partisan,

⁵⁴ IranWire, "Jin, Jiyan, Azadi: The Resonance of the Women's Movement in Kurdistan," IranWire, May 8, 2023,

⁵⁵ Radio Farda, "Iranian Protesters Face Increasing Violence from Security Forces," Radio Farda, September 16, 2022,

⁵⁶ Shadyar Omrani, "Jin, Jiyan, Azadi: The Resonance of the Women's Movement in Kurdistan," IranWire, May 8, 2023,

⁵⁷ Radio Farda, "24 Hours in Saqqez: The Burial of Mahsa Amini," Radio Farda, September 19, 2023,

⁵⁸ BBC News, "Iranian Women Protest Against Compulsory Hijab," BBC News, February 5, 2018,

⁵⁹VOA News, "Shiva Mohabbobi: At Least 60,000 People Have Been Arrested Across Iran So Far" (November 18, 2022),

⁶⁰ BBC News. "At Least 22,000 Detainees' Participation in Protests Confirmed; Most of the Released Were Not in Prison." March 13, 2023.

⁶¹ Hengaw, "Hengaw Statistical Report on the Killing of at Least 134 Kurdish Citizens During the Jina Revolution" (March 11, 2023),

⁶²Ibid.

⁶³ Maryam Sinaiee, "IRGC Agency Official's Arrest Confirms Authenticity Of Leaked Files," Iran International, June 12, 2022, accessed May 16, 2024,

and current-driven".⁶⁴ Official and media statements further amplify that a substantial portion of the demonstrators, as much as 93% according to the Javan newspaper, were under 25 years old.⁶⁵

The scope of the WLF protests, as evidenced by mass demonstrations across more than 144 universities and numerous high schools in Iran, led to significant repercussions, with at a large-yet-contestable number of students arrested.⁶⁶⁶⁷

The BBC notes that the scale of these protests mirrors those of 2017 and 2019, yet the participant demographics and dynamics hark back to the 2009 protests. Similarities to the 2019 protests include the methods of suppression, the alarming number of children among the fatalities, slogans explicitly opposing the government, and significant mobilization in Kurdish regions.⁶⁸ The continuity of protests, emergence of middle-class issues, global support, and backing from artists and athletes, both domestically and internationally, draw parallels with the 2009 protests,⁶⁹ albeit with a broader target group in the recent movement. Another distinct feature of the recent protests, compared to earlier ones, is the active involvement of syndicate guilds in organizing strikes, reminiscent of the 1979 petroleum workers' strikes, signaling a broader base of organizational support and solidarity with the movement.

The regional distribution of the protests in Iran during 2022 showed significant activity in Kurdish majority provinces such as Ilam, Kermanshah, Kurdistan, and West Azerbaijan, with 18% of demonstrations occurring there. The fatalities reported from these protests were disproportionately high among Kurdish (32%) and Baloch (30%) populations.⁷⁰ The heightened intensity of protests in these regions can be attributed to several factors, including the larger population sizes in Tehran and Esfahan, which naturally host more protesters.⁷¹ The Kurdish community, in particular, has shown strong resonance with the protest movement, especially in Kurdistan and West Azerbaijan provinces, likely fueled by the death of Mahsa Amini, a Kurd from Saghez in Kurdistan Province. Despite Kurdistan's smaller population, it experienced a substantial number of protest incidents, surpassing even Tehran, which has a much larger population.⁷²

⁶⁴ Iran International, "IRGC Commander-in-Chief Admits to Widespread Youth Participation in Protests," October 10, 2022,

⁶⁵ Khabar Online, "10,800 People Arrested in 'Recent Tehran Disturbances' + Details," January 11, 2023,

⁶⁶ VOA News, "Iran Protests Death Toll Rises to 495," December 16, 2022

⁶⁷ Human Rights Activists News Agency (HRANA), "Iran Protests 2022 - Detailed Report of 20 Days of Nationwide Protests in Iran," Human Rights Activists, ISBN 978-1-7370668-4-2,

⁶⁸ BBC Persian, "The Connection, Similarities, and Differences of Protests in 1401 with 88, 96, and 98" (October 14, 2022), <https://www.bbc.com/persian/articles/cw4ngndq3dwo>.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ ACLED, "Anti-Government Demonstrations in Iran: A Long-Term Challenge for the Islamic Republic," April 12, 2023

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² Ibid.

The "Data Analysis of the Mahsa Amini Protest Movement" (2022) by Critical Threats (CT) at the Institute For the Study of War (ISW) documented the fluctuating scale of the protests, with daily events peaking in September and declining by December.⁷³ The major hubs of protest activity were Tehran, Esfahan, Kurdistan, and West Azerbaijan, accounting for nearly 40% of the total.⁷⁴ Although there were attempts to organize nationwide demonstrations subsequently, these did not achieve the same level of participation as before, likely due to the intensified crackdown by the Iranian regime, including the issuance of death sentences and the deployment of IRGC Ground Forces in Kurdish-majority areas, employing severe measures to suppress the protests.⁷⁵

In February 2023, a survey by Ammar Maleki conducted through the GAMAAN institute, provided crucial insights into Iranian public opinion regarding the 2022 nationwide protests.⁷⁶ This extensive survey involved approximately 200,000 participants, with a significant majority residing within Iran, offering a representative glimpse into the attitudes of literate Iranian adults aged 19 and above.⁷⁷

A striking 81% of respondents from within Iran expressed rejection of the IR when posed with the question "Islamic Republic: Yes or No?". Further inquiries into preferred governance models revealed diverse opinions: 28% of domestic respondents favored a presidential republic, 12% a parliamentary republic, and 22% showed a preference for a constitutional monarchy. These preferences varied somewhat among respondents outside Iran.⁷⁸ Participation in protest activities varied, with 22% of respondents within Iran reporting participation in street protests, and a larger segment, 53%, expressed openness to future involvement.⁷⁹ Support for oppositional activities, such as nightly chanting, was also significant.⁸⁰

A notable 85% of pro-protest respondents within Iran endorsed the idea of a 'Coalition Council' or opposition coalition, encompassing activists from various political backgrounds.⁸¹ Opinions on the composition of such a council varied, with a substantial proportion advocating for inclusion of activists both within and outside Iran, while others preferred a council based solely on domestic or diaspora activists.

⁷³ Zachary Coles, "Data Analysis of the Mahsa Amini Protest Movement," December 22, 2022, ISW Press

⁷⁴ Ibid.

⁷⁵ Ibid.

⁷⁶ Ammar Maleki and Pooyan Tamimi Arab, "Iranians' Attitudes Toward the 2022 Nationwide Protests," February 4, 2023, GAMAAN

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Ibid.

⁸⁰ Ibid.

⁸¹ Ibid.

The survey also sought opinions on potential members of a Coalition Council, leading to a list of ten popular figures from diverse political and social spheres. Subsequently, the crown prince Reza Pahlavi, football player Ali Karimi, activist Esmailiun, and journalist Alinejad, who ranked high in popularity, formed a Coalition Council, garnering an initial widespread support.

Several inferences can be posited here. The significant rejection of the IR by 81% of respondents within Iran, coupled with the varied preferences for alternative governance structures, points to an evident demand for systemic change. The active participation and willingness to engage in protests, as indicated by 22% of respondents having already taken part in street actions, amplifies the state public engagement and a readiness to support further demonstrations. The endorsement of a Coalition Council by 85% of pro-protest respondents reflects a strong inclination towards organized and collective opposition, transcending individual dissent to form a cohesive force.

These findings, when aligned with the regional distribution of protests and the significant involvement of youth, women, and ethnic minorities, particularly Kurds and Baloch, depict a movement characterized by its extensive reach and new demographic engagement.

What the aforementioned demographic information tells us, is a plausible discursive frame we can establish as the common denominators of what constitutes the ideological foundation of the WLF movement. WLF protests emerged as multidimensional and expansive, considerate of its nation-wide reach, anchoring on public discontent with the regime and driven by a collective aspiration for first and foremost *liberty* from a government that has aptly situated itself as an alienated occupying force. The interpretation of *liberty* varies for each group. Whereas for Women the emphasis on liberty is a broad focus on civil rights, for many Kurds and Baloch –which had become disenfranchised through their sunni faith– *liberty* is founded on the right to self identification and self determination.

This frame is best manifested in the slogans that emerged during the protest movement. Slogans, manifesting both as chants and graffiti during protests, serve as one of the most transparent forms of discursive acts. Slogans as succinct, potent phrases encapsulate the core messages and objectives of a movement, enabling participants to collectively articulate their grievances, aspirations, and calls to action.

4.2. Slogans as streams

Slogans, manifesting both as chants and graffiti during protests, serve as a conduit of the WLF movement's ideology. These succinct discursive acts and potent phrases encapsulate the core messages and objectives of a movement, enabling participants to collectively articulate their grievances, aspirations, and calls to action.

In the analysis of protest slogans, we can categorize them into what we refer to as "streams," which embody clusters of slogans sharing similar characteristics and themes. These streams are not stable, but are rather dynamic and fluid – evolving with the changing context and episodes of the movement. They capture the temporal ethos of the movement, reflecting the prevailing sentiments and demands at any given episodic discourse.

These discursive streams serve as a foundation upon which politically charged groups can construct and adapt their discursive frames through frame alignment. By aligning their rhetoric with the dominant streams, these groups can effectively connect with a broader audience, ensuring their message remains pertinent and resonant with the public zeitgeist. Furthermore, the concept of streams conforms to the inherent plurality in the slogans used within the movement. It recognizes that various slogans, whether chanted in protests or displayed as graffiti, can coexist and be prevalent in different periods.

The initial response to Mahsa Amini's death catalyzed the *Revolutionary Stream* of protest slogans, marked by a strong anti-establishment sentiment. Dominant slogans during September and October prominently featured direct opposition to the regime, with phrases like "Death to Khamenei" and "Death to Dictator" being widely chanted. The focus was intensely personal at times, targeting the Supreme Leader, Ali Khamenei, directly with slogans like "Canons, Tanks, Firetrackers, Khamenei is a bastard" and "Khamenei is a killer, his regime is invalid," signifying a violent denouncement of the entire IR establishment.

The slogans also extended their critique to state security forces, including the Police, IRGC, voluntary paramilitary units of Basij. They often incorporated humor to amplify their appeal and memorability. Equating the Basij and IRGC with ISIS or expressing personal vengeance like "I'll kill whoever has killed my sister" once again echoed the scale of public fury against the establishment. This was as opposed to the protests in the preceding years, where the slogans and demands were dominantly devoid of violent call to actions against the IR apparatus or its total overthrow.

Amidst the escalating repression by the IR, slogans evolved to bolster participation and solidarity among the protesters. Phrases urging action, such as “Honourable Student, support, support,” aimed to galvanize student mobilization. Calls to collective action extended to “If we are not one, we will be killed one by one” and “People why are you sitting, what are you waiting fo” to further intensify the movement’s momentum, reflecting a strategic shift towards encouraging broader public involvement in the face of aggression. Reverting to Moaddel’s study of 1979 revolution, what the discursive transition of the slogans suggests, is the direct role of the crackdown mechanisms that determine the trajectory of the discursive development.

The burial of Mahsa Jina Amini marked a pivotal discursive episode in the protest movement, leading to the widespread adoption of the slogan "Woman, Life, Freedom" in both Kurdish and Persian. More so than the previous calls to violence, the WLF slogan excelled in constructing a narrative of solidarity and unity for the protest movement, under a coherent discursive frame. This slogan was not only chanted by protesters but also prominently displayed on walls and in bazaars across Iran. It is evident, through its adaption, how it has become central in the movement’s ethos. The WLF slogan didn’t displace the active slogans which called to violence, but projected a particular facade over it that emphasized a set of nearly universal values over contentious violent rhetorics. “Woman” for an opposition to the decades of gender apartheid and continued repression of Women’s civil rights; “Life” for the right to live and the right to self-determination with autonomy over oneself; “freedom”, for an emancipation from the incumbent regime, which the study of discourses suggested that it was interpreted as an occupier state more so than an authoritarian elite.

Emerging alongside "Woman, Life, Freedom" was a strong current of nationalism, sacrifice, and group identity, with slogans like “We will fight, we will die, we will get back Iran” gaining prominence in reaction to the violence meted out to protestors by law enforcement units. This nationalistic fervor was further intensified by the government’s derogatory attacks on women’s motives, leading to retorts such as “You are wanton, you are promiscuous, I am the free woman” from the female protesters.

The intensification of state violence, especially in provinces of West Azerbaijan, Kurdistan, and Sistan & Balochistan, sparked new chants emphasizing unity and solidarity across the Iranian populace against the regime. Phrases like “From [city] to [city], my life is for Iran” and “Kurdistan is not alone, Iran is behind you” echoed the collective resolve and nationwide support, resonating deeply during the most turbulent periods of the protests.

The stream identified as focusing on national unity and solidarity against the IR significantly shaped the protest's narrative, enhancing the perception of a unified front against the regime. This sentiment

was mirrored in the discursive contributions of new organizations aiming to facilitate mobilization efforts and drive regime change.

Concurrently, a distinct *Political Stream* emerged, primarily outside of Iran, characterized by the involvement of the Iranian diaspora. Despite the predominantly anti-establishment rhetoric within Iran by November, the Iranian diaspora's demonstrations, particularly in October and November, witnessed the convergence of exiled opposition groups, bringing to the fore longstanding grievances. From hereon, what the first theory presupposed –In response to the WLF's discursive juncture, legacy opposition groups competed for aligning their frame with the movement– was put to test.

A notable episode occurred during a gathering in Paris on October 2, attended by Yasmine Pahlavi, wife of the crown prince, Reza Pahlavi. Yasmine Pahlavi is among the recognizable and influential actors of the legacy opposition group, despite lacking a formative political position outside her relationship to the royal family. With her presence becoming more pronounced, initially surrounded by monarchists, the demonstrators were prompted to chant “Reza Shah may your soul rejoice” in reference to the legacy of Reza Pahlavi's grandfather, the founder of the Pahlavi dynasty. In the same gathering, surrounding Yasmine Pahlavi, left-leaning groups expressing their disdain for monarchical figures through slogans like “Death to Oppressor, be it Shah or Mullah,” directly challenging Yasmine Pahlavi's presence. This incident is set to be analyzed further in chapter 7 as an episodic discourse, marking a significant point of contention that fueled the discord between exiled left and right opposition groups. This incident is set to be analyzed further in chapter 7 as an episodic discourse, marking a significant point of contention that fueled the discord between exiled left and right opposition groups.

The slogan "Death to Oppressor, be it Shah or Mullah" was also partially resonated within Iran, especially in academic settings where the recordings of the slogans were captured. This slogan however, possibly unbeknownst to those chanting it, was appropriated by another political group that is recognized as a cult radical Islamo-Marxist⁸² within the Iranian political space.

The Mujahedin-e Khalq (MEK), who had become the most well-organized exiled opposition groups at the expense of cult-like coercion and intimidation of their members, used the adaptation of the slogan by Iranian students as a mechanism of promoting the organization's outreach and highly exaggerating its infiltration within Iranian universities, where it once held a strong support during the 1979 revolution.

⁸²Arron Merat, "Terrorists, Cultists – or Champions of Iranian Democracy? The Wild Wild Story of the MEK," *The Guardian*, November 9, 2018

This event sparked counter-chants from anti-MEK leftist groups advocating for a secular democracy free from theocracy, monarchy, or cult influences, as encapsulated in their rallying cry, “No [Supreme Leader], No Pahlavi, No cult of Rajavi, Democracy, Laïcité, Liberty, Equality.”

These developments pointed to a deepening rifts within the readily divided institution of oppositionality, with the discord now permeating back into Iran. In the city of Izeh in Khuzestan province, known for historically proactive and nationalistic demonstrations, protesters chanted “Iran is ready, command us crown prince” in alignment with monarchist sentiments, while simultaneously chanting “Death to the corrupts, Mullahs, the Leftists, the Mujahids (MEK)”. Yasmine Pahlavi's promotion of these slogans on her social media further amplified their adoption by monarchist factions in the subsequent monarchist demonstrations.

Despite the rise of a Political Stream abroad, it did not diminish the fervor of the Revolutionary Stream within Iran. Instead, it led media outlets with political affiliations to selectively highlight or distort discursive acts to bolster the agendas of particular groups. Monarchist media outlets, notably Keyhan London, Independent Persian, and ManotoTV, manipulated coverage, misrepresenting the “Woman Life Freedom” chants in Kurdish regions as “Woman Life Pahlavi” and selectively using the handful of slogan banners in support of Pahlavi used during Friday prayers demonstrations in the city of Zahedan, in Sistan & Balochistan province to amplify the support for monarchy in Iran, without reporting the slogans that were either unaligned or strongly associated with revolutionary streams. One would infer the method of frame alignment used by various groups, particularly monarchists, during the political stream was an aggressive synthesis of frame transformation and frame extension that had more emphasis on manipulation of the ground observations, more so than the promotion of the frames.

Demarcating the exact moment when the political discourse led to internal strife is challenging. However, it's apparent that this strife, the *Internecine Stream*, occurs simultaneously with the political stream, suggesting that political discourse inherently carries the potential for conflict. Understanding the emergence of these divisive discursive streams requires an examination of the frameworks that shape them. Analyzing how these frameworks interact and influence each other within the opposition's broader context is crucial to help with clarifying the mechanisms through which discourse contributes to intra-oppositional divisions and the dynamics of opposition within the protest movements.

4.3. Frames Of Oppositionality

The WLF movement marked a critical juncture in discursive institution of oppositionality. This transformation introduced diverse meanings and objectives among various groups, each aligning with distinct discursive frames, often as inherently exclusionary dialogical spaces. A central aspect of this discourse was the role of women, which emerged as a pivotal frame within the broader oppositional narrative, focusing on women's emancipation and challenging the institutions governing womanhood.

Prominent figures such as journalist Alinejad played a crucial role in shaping this discourse through initiatives like “White Wednesday” and “My Stealthy Freedom,” campaigns that not only protested against the mandatory hijab law but also fostered a wider dialogue on women's emancipation. Significant contributors to this discourse included female athletes, artists, and academics, who collectively amplified the movement's message. Many of those who supported the movement through attending international events without the mandatory Hijab –as required and regulated by the totalitarian style citizen-control apparatus– were punitively sanctioned by the government.⁸³

Alinejad's engagements with international figures, often accompanied by women directly impacted by the protests, emboldened the global resonance of the movement's call for change and the central role of women in driving the discourse on emancipation and civil rights within the institution of oppositionality.

The slogan "Woman, Life, Freedom" not only unified the protest movements but also inadvertently facilitated the introduction of Jineology, or Kurdish feminism, created by Abdullah Ocalan, into the discourses.⁸⁴ Incorporation of Jineology to the mainstream dialogic frame of womanhood also carried with it the political ideological narratives of Jineology – namely democratic confederalism. The chant "Woman, Life, Freedom" was first cried by Kurdish female brigades of Rojava, adherents of Jineology, in Syria following their liberation movement against ISIS.⁸⁵ It must however be noted that the Jineology was either temporally relevant or later cellulized within the Kurdish majority provinces, since the WLF chant and movement had later turned to a national issue with a much broader focus than just women's civil rights.

This discursive frame primarily symbolized the empowerment of women and girls, advocating for their rights under the gender apartheid system of the IR, highlighting issues such as honor killings, domestic violence, and the societal norms that uphold male dominance through the objectification of women.

⁸³ BBC Persian, "Iran Protests; Extensive Reaction of Female Athletes to Compulsory Hijab and the Death of Mahsa Amini," October 5, 2022

⁸⁴ Abdullah Ocalan, *Liberating Life: Woman's Revolution* (International Initiative Edition, 2013)

⁸⁵ Bese Hozat, "Jin, Jiyan, Azadi — Women, Life, Freedom!," Kurdish Peace Initiative, September 23, 2022

While the political ideology brought forth by Kurdish Jineology in this discourse did not resonate strongly with the broader public and media, possibly due to the rapid unfolding of events, it did normalize dialogue around federalism, democratic confederalism, and regional autonomy which were once strongly taboo topics. These topics had been marginalized on two ends: First, due to their portrayal by the IR and monarchist factions as ‘separatism’. Second, due to the crypto-separatist intentions of the advocates of federalism who often convoluted call for democratic regional autonomy within Iranian territories to aspirations of establishing of ethno-states.

Furthermore, the semantic identification of this frame is highly contestable. Alinejad, often associated with feminism, has critiqued Western feminism for its perceived failure to adequately support the rights of Iranian and Afghan women, fearing accusations of Islamophobia.⁸⁶ Conversely, Alinejad has faced criticism for allegedly not fully embracing the principles of Jineology, particularly in her deliberative engagements with Pahlavi during Coalition Council formations. Given these complexities and differing perspectives, this discursive frame is best classified as *Zananegi* or 'Womanhood,' since it fails to fit within either feminist or jineology paradigms.

The liberty ethos, *Azadegi*, emerged as the most pervasive discursive theme, uniting various groups and political blocs within the opposition. This discourse, encompassing anti-establishment sentiments, the active participation of the youth, calls for emancipation of marginalized groups, and advocacy for civil rights of the minority groups, was embraced across the spectrum of opposition actors. However, the interpretation of liberty varied among these groups, leading to diverse appropriation of this theme.

The monarchists viewed liberty primarily as the liberation of Iran from the rule of the IR. Within active spaces of discourse, liberation of Iran was posited under the articulation that the IR is an illegitimate sovereign of occupational nature. This, oddle enough, had also resonated with the confederalists. Confederalists, self-identified as Federalists, aligned *Azadegi* with the right to self-determination and autonomy from a centralist state with, often argued by ethnic interest activists, Perso-Shiite hegemonic centralization. For student groups, syndicate guilds, and other civil society organizations, the concept of *Azadegi* was contextualized to reflect the specific issues and demands pertinent to their sectors.

While the *Azadegi* frame found widespread acceptance, its interpretation and emphasis differed significantly among the groups. Nationalist republicans and monarchists often found the confederalist perspectives on the right to self-determination for minorities contentious. Such divergences in understanding and prioritizing aspects of liberty led to dialogic disagreements, accumulating to fragmentations that unfolded in the subsequent discursive episodes of the WLF movement.

⁸⁶ Masih Alinejad, "Why I'm Opposed to Ilhan Omar's Bill against Islamophobia," The Washington Post, January 25, 2022

A significant yet informally represented group within the protest demographics were the advocates of the *Republican frame*. These individuals distanced themselves from the democratic confederalist and far-left ideologies associated with the WLF movement, yet supported its overarching objectives. They conceptualized WLF as inherently a national revolution, framing it as a the collective responsibility and unity of all groups in Iran in their shared struggle.

This National Republican perspective specifically refuted the multinationality of Iranian society as advocated by cofederalists and the pan-Ummah or pan-Islamism promoted by the clerical regime. Consequently, the discourse often veered into anti-Islamic and anti-clerical rhetoric, vehemently opposing the cofederalists' alleged anti-tribal stance. Additionally, the republican aspect of this frame vehemently opposed the monarchical inclinations, particularly Pahlavist royalism, branding any return to monarchy and its constitution as regressive and antithetical to the progressive ethos of the WLF movement. This discursive stance positioned the monarchy and its supporters as 'backward' to the movement's vision of progressivism.

The emergence of the *Revivalist frame*, strongly advocated by advisors and the intimate circle of Pahlavi, introduced a contentious and hegemonic dimension to the discourse. This frame had come into the fray long before the WLF movement, but had managed to largely hegemonize a previously pluralistic and disorganized monarchist frame through the formation of Farashgard (Iran Revival Group). Farashgard consisted of forty young founding members, some with questionable backgrounds and historical ties to the government. As opposed to the ragged advocates of Monarchy preceding them, Farashgard represented a more aggressive and uncompromising stance within the monarchist spectrum. It contended with both royalists and constitutionalists to construct a monolithic unity among all patriotic factions, under the non-partisan leadership of Reza Pahlavi. Their objective was to collectively challenge the IR and determine the governance structure through a free referendum—a view consistently propagated by Reza Pahlavi himself.

While in the onset of its creation Farashgard was ought to represent both monarchists and republicans, its discourse eventually skewed distinctly towards revival of the Pahlavi monarchy, leading to its perception as purely monarchistic before its organizational dissolution. This frame notably downplayed the significance of the WLF movement, asserting that the revolutionary movement commenced with the Cyrus the Great Revolt, in an attempt to diminish the WLF movement as a discursive juncture, but a mere discursive episode of another juncture. Consequently, the political ideologies associated with the WLF movement, particularly democratic confederalism, were used as strawman to outright undermine the movement.

Both the Republican and Revivalist frames shared patriotic and anti-clerical sentiments, yet the Revivalist perspective uniquely linked clericalism with the left, often encompassing republicanism. The Revivalist discourse, using pejorative labels such as Cult of Madness (Ferqe Jonun) for anti-monarchist elements of the WLF movement, equated these groups with the 1979 revolution's actors, derogatorily referred to as “Panjah-o hafti/57y.” This framing effectively attempted to monopolize the definition of legitimate opposition to those supporting Pahlavi, sidelining republican critical of Pahlavi and merely tolerating non-monarchist Pahlavi supporters. This stance would shift frequently as the consequential inability of the monarchists to create a space of collaboration outside their cluster.

Efforts to hegemonize the opposition's discourse included disparaging the "Woman Life Freedom" slogan with vulgarities such as “Woman Life Circumcision,” exploiting a false stereotypes about Kurds, and “Woman Life Kalashnikov,” mocking Kurdish armed resistance. Alternative slogans proposed by this frame, such as “Man Nation Prosperity” or “King Nation Prosperity,” aimed to dilute the original message, with the former even appearing in Pahlavi's social media bio, suggested as a more gender inclusive slogan for the movement. However, this adoption sparked controversy, with critics alleging that Pahlavi's circle might be compromised by infiltrated operatives, a claim fueled by the slogan's use in a performance supporting Major General Qassem Soleimani, an assassinated commander of the IRGC Quds force.

As opposed to the groups on the left of the political spectrum which attempted to align their frames with the WLF through bridging, amplification and extension, the most pronoucnly observed mechanism adopted by the revivalist frame was a synthesis of alienation of the movements' advocates, diminishing the discursive juncture through emphasis on its sequential discursive episodes, denial of grounded observations, spread of false, tempered and disinformation as a mechanism of amplification.

In May 2023, the brief removal and subsequent reinstatement of these slogans from Pahlavi's social media profile garnered significant reaction, with Pahlavi's detractors and his staunchest supporters supporting the brief divorce of the crown prince from the WLF movement.

The Confederalist frame –otherwise "Nationalities under Oppression" (Melliat haye taht Setam)– prominently featured in discussions on platforms such as X and ClubHouse, as well as interviews on Iran International News, highlighted the grievances of cofederalist advocates, who essentially supported a confederalist governance structure. Their frame emphasized the disproportionate violence and systemic discrimination faced by Kurdish and Baloch communities in Iran, attributing these issues to the centralized power and dominance of Persian and Shiite governance. Figures like Abdollah

Mohtadi of the Kurdish Komala party, Khaled Azizi of the PDKI, Ali Javanmardi, a journalist and political activist based in the Kurdish Region of Iraq (KRG), and other supporters of ethnic federalism, argued for acknowledging Iran's diversity of nationalities and the emancipation of non-Persian ethnic groups as essential outcomes of the WLF movement.

Advocates of this frame often positioned their discourse in opposition to Pahlavi supporters, labeling the latter as *fascists* and their discursive tactics as *totalitarian*. The increasing focus on Pahlavi was derisively termed as "Sounds of the footsteps of fascist." Moreover, nationalist republicans who rejected the concept of Iran's multinationality faced pejorative labels like "Farshist" (Persian and Fascist) for Persians, or "Faschismile" (Fascist and Assimilated) for non-Persian speakers, further illustrating the intense discursive contention and the construction of exclusionary narratives within the protest movement.

During the WLF movement, various frames emerged that catered to specific societal sectors without necessarily engaging in the broader political discourse. Student-centered frames, for example, concentrated on the pivotal role of youth and students in the protests, emphasizing educational and rights-based issues without delving into political agendas. Similarly, frames related to syndicate guilds, representing diverse groups like teachers, nurses, workers, farmers, bazaaris, and truck drivers, focused on sector-specific concerns and often consciously steered clear of the political dynamics of the protests.

On the other hand, the activities of region-specific human rights organizations straddled the line between being apolitical and politically involved. Organizations such as Hyrcania, focusing on the southern Caspian region, Hengaw for Kurdish areas, and Halvsh for Sistan and Balochistan, primarily provided localized information. However, they occasionally and intentionally interwove politically charged narratives within their discourse, leading to accusations of exploiting the human rights label to advance political objectives. This tactic was however not conspiratorial. Most active Human Rights organizations were supported by politically charged organizations. For instance, the Baloch Raji Tepaki Gel (BNS) separatist party used its Human Rights Committee, known as Rasad of Balochistan, to promote separatism and national sovereignty for the Baloch people in the parallel efforts to cover human rights violations in the region.

The relationship between these frames can be conceptualized with the same terms of symbiotic relations between organizations. These relationships are dynamic and can change overtime with occurrence of new episodic developments.

4.3.1 Mutualist Frames (low tension)

Mutualist frames within the discourse of the WLF movement are characterized by their harmonious and reinforcing nature, devoid of tension and conflict. During debates on mainstream opposition networks or independent media, proponents of frames centered on Zananegi, Azadegi, and Syndicate guilds engage in a constructive dialogical process. These interactions facilitate an exchange of ideas that bolsters the diversity of the movement's discursive field without hampering another frame.

4.3.2 Acquiescent Frames (medium tension)

Acquiescent frames are characterized by some level of tension, yet they facilitate productive dialogue within the discourse. When discursive overlaps occur, these frames allow for compromise in consensus deliberation to sustain unity and reduce internal discord. A notable instance of this is seen in the interactions between provincial federalism advocates and national republicans. Despite their differences, both groups occasionally yield on matters such as the territorial integrity of Iran and the push for systemic decentralization to minimize oppositional friction.

This willingness to compromise leads to the development of new discursive frames born out of dialogical synthesis. For example, the nuanced position of "National Federalists," which lacks direct political representation, has emerged from the amalgamation of the National Republican and Federalist perspectives.

The dynamics of frame relationships extend beyond simple binary interactions. An illustration of this complexity is the nuanced compromise among Ethnic Right Advocates, Feminists, Pahlavists, and Republicans concerning anti-Islamic discourse. Given the strong anti-Islamic sentiment due to grievances with the IR over four decades, the protest actions in Balochistan, often occurring before Friday Islamic prayers and led by Molana Abdulhamid, necessitated a careful adjustment of discourse. This adjustment ensured that anti-clerical and anti-Islamic sentiments did not alienate or offend the ethnic-rights advocates, particularly within the Baloch community. The objective was to maintain a delicate balance within acquiescent frames to foster inclusivity and respect among diverse groups as the result of a dialectical oppositionism.

4.3.3 Competitive Frames (high tension)

Politically competitive frames, predominant in the political stream, align with Stilberg's notion that frames are more about striving for hegemony than fostering consensus. These frames are observable in the actions of ideologically left-leaning parties aiming to broaden their sway within the opposition,

often by discrediting other leftist groups as inauthentic. This competitive dynamic is evident in the divisions within organizations like the Fadayian and Komala parties, as well as within nationalist factions such as the National Front, which will be explored further in subsequent discussions.

The competitiveness of a frame is not static; it evolves in response to the changing terrain of a protest movement. For example, the Revivalist frame initially capitalized on the nostalgia of greater liberties for women during the Pahlavi era, including advancements from the white revolution like voting, work, and education rights. Many revivalists contended that Pahlavism inherently embodied the principles of the WLF movement, citing the Pahlavi family's female members as evidence of a pro-feminist stance.⁸⁷ However, the dynamics shifted notably following the alleged fallout between Alinejad and Pahlavi and the unsuccessful formation of the Coalition Council. This shift turned the relationship between the Zananegi and Revivalism frames from one of acquiescence to outright competition.

These discursive frames reveal themselves during the discursive episodes are contingent on the core institutions of the opposition groups. While chapter 4.3 addressed the frames that emerge in subsequent episodes of the WLF critical juncture, anatomizing the oppositionality and accounting for the ideological foundations of the legacy groups enables establishing better inference on their motivation to manifest their discursive frames as competitive. The subsequent chapter addresses this specific issue, by contextualizing the oppositionality prior to the WLF's discursive juncture with the objective to infer if their background is reflective of their post revolution behaviour.

⁸⁷ VOA News, "Yasamin Pahlavi said in the Nowruz program of Voice of America that my husband is a true feminist," 2021, Balatarin,

5. Anatomizing The Exiled Opposition

5.1. Legacy Opposition

The 1987 study by Annabelle Sreberny-Mohammadi and Ali Mohammadi titled “Post-Revolutionary Iranian Exiles: A Study in Impotence” remarkably echoes current observations of the ineffectiveness and fragmented nature of the Iranian opposition in exile.⁸⁸ The authors contend that the potential for regime change in Iran is more likely to be found within the country, possibly with figures such as the then prime minister, Bazargan, or emerging groups within the IR, rather than with the disparate and disorganized exiled opposition.⁸⁹

Sreberny-Mohammadi and Mohammadi criticize the exile groupings as remnants of the Pahlavi era, afflicted by the same political culture defects: deep-seated mistrust among members, fierce competition for leadership, and a pervasive individualism that hinders lasting coalition-building.⁹⁰ In the context of discursive framing, the authors perceive the opposition's rigid stances as predominantly Competitive Frames, noting an ideological inflexibility that allows minor disagreements to overshadow vast areas of agreement, thus obstructing pragmatic politics.⁹¹

The study categorizes the exiled opposition into four main blocs: The Left, The Monarchists, The Islamic Republican, and The Reformist. The Left bloc, comprising the Fedayeen-e-Khalq and the Tudeh Party, regained prominence during the 1977-79 movement, with the Fedayeen notably active in the street battles against monarchy forces, contributing significantly to the establishment of the Islamic Republic. However, the Fedayeen quickly splintered over disagreements regarding the Provisional Government's class nature and the emerging dynamics within the revolutionary structure, including debates over the rising petty-bourgeoisie's role and the influence of liberal, pro-capitalist elements. The majority Fedayeen prioritized the anti-imperialist struggle, advocating support for the IR against external threats, while the minority faction, led by Deghani, adopted an anti-Khomeinist stance, arguing that the revolution was incomplete and needed to continue its course.⁹²

The study reveals that monarchist politicians were embroiled in infighting, mirroring the divisive nature of the broader political exile community. Efforts to consolidate monarchist forces, such as the 1980 initiative by monarchist right-wingers to form the Saviour Front (Jebhe Nejat) with Ali Amini, aimed to counter the Islamic fundamentalist regime but ultimately faltered.

⁸⁸ Annabelle Sreberny-Mohammadi and Ali Mohammadi, *Post-Revolutionary Iranian Exiles: A Study in Impotence*, p.108

⁸⁹ *Ibid.* p.109

⁹⁰ *Ibid.* p.126

⁹¹ *Ibid.*

⁹² *Ibid.* p.111

This council sought to rally exiled Iranians for the Pahlavi restoration with constitutional modifications akin to the Spanish monarchy model. Shahpour Bakhtiar, the final prime minister under the Shah, instead advocated for a constitutional monarchy and preferred a public referendum to decide the monarchy's fate in Iran, aligning more with European constitutional models. Disagreements between Shahpour Bakhtiar, the final prime minister under the Shah, and Pahlavi was quoted as the cause of the council's dissolution.⁹³

Bakhtiar's disdain for potential allies was clear, labeling NCRI (rebranded MEK) founders Bani-Sadr and Rajavi as "Clown" and "Fanatic," respectively, and viewing the leftist coalition as Moscow's puppet, rejecting any collaboration with them.⁹⁴

The NCRI formed in 1981 in Paris, comprised political entities and individuals initially involved in establishing the IR but later alienated by the regime's oppressive tactics. This council included diverse groups like the MEK, PDKI, National Democratic Front, and smaller socialist factions, alongside ex-president Bani-Sadr.⁹⁵ Bani-Sadr and Rajavi's flight to Paris facilitated the creation of the NCRI, an umbrella group aiming to unify all opposition factions against the IR, positing itself as a government-in-waiting to replace Khomeini's regime, with Bani-Sadr as President and Rajavi leading the provisional government.⁹⁶

Massoud Rajavi, leader of the Mojahedin-e-Khalq (MEK), asserted that peaceful methods were insufficient to topple Khomeini's regime, initiating an armed struggle. Tehran became a battleground between the urban guerrillas, primarily the MEK, and the regime's forces, including the Revolutionary Guards (IRGC) and Hezbollah units. The IR responded with severe repression: clamping down on demonstrations, confiscating publications, raiding safe houses, and filling prisons with political dissenters.⁹⁷ The regime, under the judicial oversight of Ebrahim Raisi, now IR's president, allegedly executed 20,000 dissidents, earning Raisi the moniker "butcher of Tehran" from the opposition.⁹⁸

The PDKI, under Rahman Qassemlou, initially supported the Islamic Revolution but soon presented a set of demands for federalism and self-determination. The onset of the Iran-Iraq War saw the PDKI offering a ceasefire and cooperation against the Iraqi forces, contingent on the central government meeting its demands. Instead, Khomeini called for jihad against both the Kurds and Iraqis, driving the PDKI towards the NCRI, which increasingly relied on Iraqi financial support.⁹⁹

⁹³ Ibid. p.120

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ Ibid. p.110

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Ibid. p.112

⁹⁸ i24NEWS. "'Butcher of Tehran' Cutouts Warn NYC of Iranian President Arrival at UNGA." September 15, 2023.

⁹⁹ Annabelle Sreberny-Mohammadi and Ali Mohammadi, *Post-Revolutionary Iranian Exiles: A Study in Impotence*, p.110

Rajavi's alignment with Saddam and his aggressive tactics alienated him from other political entities, including Bani-Sadr, who likened Rajavi to a suicidal figure. The MEK's cult-like behavior and ideological extremism led to comparisons with Pol Pot's Khmer Rouge, with concerns that their ascendancy might result in retaliatory mass violence.¹⁰⁰

Reflecting on the current state of opposition in Iran, it is apparent that the same divisive flaws that characterized the political terrain post-revolution persist, rooted in the foundational structures of the four principal blocs. By the 2020s, two movements that were prominent in the 1980s, the NCRI and the reformist Liberation Front, faced widespread denunciation.¹⁰¹ The NCRI, once a notable opposition entity, found itself isolated, criticized for its past alignment with Saddam during the Iran-Iraq War and its uncanny totalitarian similarities to the IR.¹⁰² Recent surveys by the Gamaan Institute indicate the NCRI's support has plummeted to less than 1%, underscoring its pariah status even amidst calls for solidarity. Any expressed support for the current president-elect of the NCRI, Maryam Rajavi, and the NCRI remains marginal and isolated within the discourse.¹⁰³

The reformist movement, despite its initial vigor, has seen its influence wane, as evidenced in both the IR's parliamentary elections and GAMAAN's polling data. The public perceives reformism as merely a cosmetic alteration of the IR's facade, a sentiment exacerbated by the disenchantment following Rouhani's administration and the tragic November protests leading to an alleged 1500 deaths in the span of a week.¹⁰⁴ Consequently, polities such as the Liberation Front, once pivotal in the revolutionary fervor, have fallen into disrepute, with the term '*enzeva*' meaning ostracized, aptly capturing their diminished standing in Iranian society.¹⁰⁵

What remained as functional oppositional institution –at the onset of the WLF movement– which could engage as a discursive actor frames, can be categorized into the following four groups: Republicans (with a margin of Socialists republicans), Monarchists, Confederalists, Non-partisans.

5.2.1 Republican Bloc

Over the years, the National Front fragmented and diversified into several branches and new entities. Some segments of the organization transitioned into the Toilers Party of the Iranian Nation (Jebhe Zahmatkeshā Iran) and the National Democratic Front (Jebhe Democratic-e Melli), both of which

¹⁰⁰ Ibid. p.116

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² Ibid.

¹⁰³ GAMAAN. "Iran's Political Systems Survey: 2022." GAMAAN, 2022.

¹⁰⁴ Michael Lipin and Katherine Ahn, "US Confirms Report Citing Iran Officials as Saying 1,500 Killed in Protests," VOA News,

¹⁰⁵ One of the frequently used chants by the protestors in 2022 was "Reformists, Principlists, this is over!"

briefly aligned with the NCRI. The principal branch within Iran has consistently supported political candidates, thus aligning with the reformist policies.¹⁰⁶

In 2007, the Iran National Front – Organizations Abroad (INF-OA) was established, echoing the ideological underpinnings of Mossadegh's National Front and maintaining a systematic opposition to the IR. The evolution continued with the formation of the 6th National Front (Saman Sheshom) in 2018, following the departure of key members from the 5th National Front.¹⁰⁷ This group was subsequently renamed the National Front of Iran and Europe (NFIE), persisting in its staunch opposition to the Islamic Revolution.¹⁰⁸ According to a 2019 GAMAAN institute survey, the National Front collectively garnered 10.8% popularity among Iranians.¹⁰⁹

To bolster the secular republican opposition, the Union for the Secular Republic and Human Rights in Iran (USRHR) was established in 2010, amalgamating smaller parties and prominent activists.¹¹⁰ This coalition included the United Republicans of Iran (URI), led by Hassan Shariatmadari, son of the influential Grand Ayatollah Seyyed Kazem Shariatmadari, a leading religious figure in the 1960s and 1970s.¹¹¹

A pivotal moment in the efforts to unify Republican advocates was the establishment of the Hamgami for the Secular Democratic Republic in Iran, a coalition bridging the political spectrum within Republican circles.¹¹² This coalition brought together diverse groups such as the United Republicans of Iran (URI), the Union for the Secular Republic and Human Rights in Iran (USRHR), the National Front of Iran and Europe (NFIE), the Iran National Front – Organizations Abroad (INF-OA), and the Left Party of Iran (LPI).¹¹³ It is unknown how strong of a reach the Hamgami movement poses. However, if the social media numbers are indicators of mobilization capacity, then Hamgami has been defunct since its creation. Fewer people follow Hamgami on its social media platforms than the smallest coalition member.

The LPI emerged in 2018 as a consolidation effort led by the Majority Party of Fadaiyan, amalgamating various smaller left-leaning entities. This move aimed to reposition the historically

¹⁰⁶ Nahzat-e Melli-e Iran, "What Happened in the 1980s?" Melliun, September 5, 2009,

¹⁰⁷ Jebhe Melli Iran and Europe, "Statement of the Establishment of the Sixth National Front in the Name of the Great Nation of Iran," Jebhe Melli Iran, November 20, 2018,

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.

¹⁰⁹ GAMAAN 2022

¹¹⁰ Iranian Republic, "Charter of the Union for Secular Republic," Iranian Republic, November 2, 2014

¹¹¹ Darius Kadivar, "VOA OFOGH: Crown Prince Reza Debates with Hassan Shariatmadari on Secularism," Iranian.com, December 5, 2012

¹¹² Hamgami. "Hamgami for Secular Democratic Republic in Iran: Principles." Hamgami. Accessed May 15, 2024. <https://hamgami.org/mabani>.

¹¹³ Ibid.

marginalized left factions from the 1979 revolution as social democrats, despite their original Leninist, Marxist, and Maoist orientations. According to GAMAAN institute surveys, these exiled left opposition parties, including Fadaiyan and Kar, garnered less than 1% popularity among Iranians, indicating a significant decline in domestic support for groups associated with the 1979 revolutionary actors.

The persistent fragmentation, adherence to outdated principles, frequent restructuring, and a general reluctance to engage with other political entities and figures have arguably contributed to the inability of Republican political groups to engage effectively with the broader Iranian republican populace. This situation has led to an entrenched defensive posture, characterized by a rejection of consensus-building efforts with other opposition factions, further isolating these groups within the political landscape of the Iranian opposition.

5.2.2 Monarchist Bloc

Iranian Monarchism can be classified into two groups based on their most observable denominator: the Royalists and the Constitutionalists. The Royalists are loyal to the Pahlavi family, while the Constitutionalists are loyal to the Iranian constitutional revolution and the legacy of constitutional legalism in Iran. Much of Iranian history has arguably been a dialectical struggle between these two revolutionary forces. While the Royalists profess absolute subservience to the will and command of the Monarch and his family, the Constitutionalists posit that the Monarch is a symbol of Iranian political legacy, and the rule of law determined by the representatives of the citizens (Majles) stands above all. Both groups have had drifts and a tug of war to gain influence over the Pahlavi's decisions and the frame of monarchism.

Parliamentarism was the product of the Iranian constitutional revolution of 1906,¹¹⁴ which subverted the then-ruling family, the Qajars, to the will of the Parliament. However, the coup d'état of Reza Shah, the founder of the Pahlavi dynasty, against the Qajars resulted in the dissolution of the parliament and its executive powers.¹¹⁵

The National Resistance Movement of Iran (NAMIR), founded by Shapour Bakhtiar, stands as one of the oldest entities opposing the IR. The assassination of Bakhtiar ended NAMIR and resulted in a lack of organizational structure for the proponents of constitutionalism. While constitutionalists were initially skeptical of Reza Pahlavi in the 1980s, citing his lavish, party-like lifestyle¹¹⁶, his coming of

¹¹⁴ M. Reza Ghods, "Iranian Nationalism and Reza Shah," *Middle Eastern Studies* 27, no. 1 (January 1991): 35-45,

¹¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁶ Kenneth R. Timmerman, *Countdown to Crisis: The Coming Nuclear Showdown with Iran* (New York: Three Rivers Press, 2006). p.49

age in the subsequent decades bridged the gap between the two camps of Royalists and Constitutionalists.

Pahlavi played a delicate balance between maintaining his Royalist support and Constitutional support, which resulted in contradictory positions and actions over time. In his earliest interviews, he had said that he considers himself to be the legal sovereign of Iran, with his oldest daughter being his heir in case of the reestablishment of the monarchy in Iran. Conversely, he had also said he does not seek any political position in Iran and that his only life mission is to assist in the liberation of the country. More contradictions have become apparent in recent years, as once again his position changed to being a defender of the civil class in Iran – a monarchical title given to an earlier Iranian Shah, Karim Khan Zand.

Pahlavi has openly declared monarchy as a violation of his human rights and the right to self-determination. He has stated he prefers a republican model of governance for Iran, while arguing his condition for accepting monarchy is an electoral monarchy, which has a precedent in Iran. This is attested by his being opinionated on many subjects, which translates to his intentions to act politically in a post-IR Iran. Very frequently, he has also positioned himself as a conduit of democratic transition if and when a revolution to overthrow the IR occurs.

Despite his claim to non-partisan leadership of the opposition, he exclusively endorses those who call for the restoration of the monarchy. While actively advocating his role as a unifier of the opposition, his selected closest advisors have contributed significantly to the slandering campaigns of the IR against the opposition, calling the WLF movement a cult of madness¹¹⁷, threatening to operationalize a violent vanguard of Iranian nationalism against their detractors¹¹⁸, calling for the creation of a nationalist socialist movement to counter anti-monarchy leftist groups¹¹⁹, and making recurring attempts to diminish the role of women and ethnic minorities in the WLF movement¹²⁰.

¹¹⁷ Amir Etemadi (@amiretemadi), "We are at a stage where boycotting the distractions of #CultOfMadness is even more important than the successful boycott of the #ElectionCircus. Their livelihood depends on getting reactions from us," X, March 18, 2024, 5:56 PM,

¹¹⁸ Samad Agha (@SamadAgha5791), "This tweet by Saeed Ghasseminejad is astonishing as is, but if you read between the lines, it becomes even more astonishing! Ignoring all those between the lines, who determines the boundary between sharp and soft angles? For example, Majidreza Rahnavard, who all these people have analyzed multiple times based on the tattoo on his hand, falls into which angle?" Twitter, March 22, 2023, 3:18 PM, <https://twitter.com/SamadAgha5791/status/1638575977340051460>.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

¹²⁰ Iran International, "Outlook; Prince Reza Pahlavi and the Extreme Right and Left / Debate between Faraj Sarkouhi and Alireza Kiani," YouTube video, May 13, 2024,

These positions have also been most echoed by Pahlavi's partner, Yasmin Pahlavi, whose social media engagement is nearly limited to the promotion of monarchy, its advocates, repetition of any ongoing political trend, and hostile antagonism of non-Monarchists.

The observation that there is a great cleavage between Pahlavi and his faith-and-flag supporters has been attested by many who have worked closely with him¹²¹. The rift is rooted in expectations of the crown prince. While many of his supporters, including his circle of advisors, consider him the methodical, political, and spiritual successor to his strongman grandfather, Reza Shah, Pahlavi himself has modeled his pathos and ethos after leaders of non-violent political resistance movements such as Nelson Mandela, Gandhi, and Martin Luther King Jr.¹²²

There are several contradictions observed in the discursive acts of Pahlavi. It is unclear whether these contradictions stem from incompetency in the deliberation of his position or an overarching strategy to justify his inability to maintain a solid stance. Nonetheless, he has maintained an erroneous balance between royalism and constitutionalism.

The Monarchist political bloc, while mostly united under Pahlavi, can be further broken down by traditional demarcations between conservatives and liberals. This breakdown is necessary, as subsequent chapters will reveal how certain factions within each political bloc contributed to the solidarity-building and the fragmentation discourse.

The conservative royalists, henceforth Sultanists, believe in the role of Pahlavi as the sole leader and conduit of transition to the pre-IR era. They adhere to the most conservative positions of Pahlavi while opposing his soft and liberal stance on various political and social issues.

The liberal royalists are best characterized as the Revivalists or the Farashgard group. This group has the greatest observed leverage of influence over Pahlavi's actions. Liberal royalists adhere to capitalistic liberal values with strong resistance towards traditionalism, which is either manifested in limiting the political role of a monarch or implementing characteristically social programs. Liberal royalists are the closest analogy to the current principlist capitalist political parties within the IR polity. Outside their position on the mode of governance and secular civil liberties, their manifested policies do not diverge greatly from the principlist capitalists.

Conservative constitutionalists, or Mashruteh, can be addressed as simply Constitutionalists. As opposed to royalists who hold Pahlavi above the monarchy, the constitutionalists believe the legacy of

¹²¹ Karim Sadjadpour, "Why Did the 'Georgetown' Meeting and the Coalition of Opponents of the Islamic Republic Collapse?" interview by Mehrad Vaezi-Nejad, Aasoo, May 14, 2024, <https://www.aasoo.org/fa/articles/4773>.

¹²² Ibid.

Iranian monarchism is parliamentarianism along with the traditions of righteous governance. To the constitutionalists, Reza Pahlavi does not bear the responsibility of leading the movement but rather leading the transition. They are principlist in the legalistic aspect, holding the primacy of the rule of law above all.

The final cluster, liberal constitutionalists or simply liberal monarchists, are characterized by loose ideas and threads of policy that do not fit the traditional sense of Iranian monarchy and do not fall under the aforementioned three groups. This includes those supporting Pahlavi's proposed electoral monarchy and the other contradictory positions of the crown prince, which have been considerably less antagonistic against other opposition groups.

What has become more evident over time is that all four categories orbit with varying distances around the figure of Reza Pahlavi – part as the bearer of the Pahlavi name, and part as the best-known opposition figure with a clean sheet track record.

The cleansheet is a double edge sword. It lacks corruption as it lacks action. Reza Pahlavi is recognized for initiating numerous projects and initiatives over the past four decades, despite many not fully reaching their goals.

In 2013, Pahlavi launched the National Council of Iran for Free Elections (NCIFE), positioning it as a broad platform supporting electoral freedom and referendum advocacy in Iran. While the council was not exclusively monarchist, departures from the coalition pointed to a perceived dominance of Pahlavism in its operations. Pahlavi stepped down from his leadership roles in 2017, claiming the organization had evolved to operate independently of his direct involvement.¹²³

The Phoenix Project of Iran, initiated by Pahlavi in 2018, aimed to consolidate the expertise of Iranian scientists towards addressing national challenges, including environmental issues and legal reform. However, the project, also known as Qoqnus, faced criticism for not producing tangible results and allegedly obstructing similar scientific endeavors, as noted by prominent figures such as Firouz Naderi and Nik Ahang Kosar.¹²⁴

On March 11, Masood Masjoody, a former founding member of Farashgard and Vice President of the Council of Iranian Canadians (CIC), initiated a legal action against Reza Pahlavi in the Supreme Court

¹²³ Baktash Khamsehpour, "Reza Pahlavi Resigns from the Presidency of the 'National Council of Iran'," Radio Farda, September 17, 2017,

¹²⁴ Iran International, "Final Word with Pouria Zareati - The Water War is Coming," YouTube video, June 23, 2023

of British Columbia, Vancouver.¹²⁵ The lawsuit alleges defamation and harassment by social media accounts linked to Pahlavi, targeting his critics, with one of the defendants reportedly being an employee of Qoqnu.¹²⁶

Masjoody's revelations of private communications within Farashgard have exposed the extent of the group's sway over Pahlavi, suggesting an indelible link with core Pahlavist ideology. Farashgard, from its inception, posited itself as the unifying force of the opposition. However, the narrative advanced by Farashgard precluded any engagement with reformist and leftist groups, branding them as responsible for the 1979 revolution's "unholy alliance" of Communists (reds) and Islamists (blacks). Moreover, Farashgard, purporting to represent the younger opposition faction, alienated the older generation of the opposition, leading to criticism from leaders of both monarchist and republican blocs. This strategy of generational exclusion resurfaced during the recent protests, with Farashgard attempting to discredit those outside its Pahlavist allegiance by pejoratively labeling them as "mentally 57y," irrespective of their actual age.

Despite its purported widespread support, Farashgard's ambitious plan to mobilize a million demonstrators on Azadi street for the "Meydun Mellyuni Campaign"¹²⁷ advocating for regime change, ultimately fell short of expectations. Farashgard members have self-attributed the orchestration of leadership training during 2018 and 2019, although such claims lack any validation.

The exposure of Farashgard's private communications, through Masjoody's legal compliant, illuminated their strategic dissemination of disinformation, notably in disassociating certain members by falsely affiliating them with the IR to justify their expulsion. This tactic of hegemonization mirrors broader strategies employed by the group to marginalize dissenting opposition factions.

Further scrutiny of these communications unveiled Farashgard's intimate connections with the Pahlavi family. Amirhossein Etemadi, later accused of 'stealing' social media accounts of Farashgard members due to strategic disagreements, emerged as the key advisor to Reza Pahlavi, significantly influencing his social media presence.¹²⁸ Yasmine Pahlavi's interactions with the group suggest at least one attempt

¹²⁵ Masood Masjoody (@MasoodMasjoody), "Complaint against @PahlaviReza, owners (currently anonymous) of some organizational accounts of #PahlaviCult, and Qasem-Shahri's minions of the cult in Vancouver," Twitter, January 9, 2024, <https://twitter.com/MasoodMasjoody/status/1744774051560870143>.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ Iran Novin Party, "Million-Man Square and Farashgard in Iran," YouTube video playlist, https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLoRy_EwZAZul3bMiY2RLqj0k2o2vS2uzj.

¹²⁸ Masood Masjoody (@MasoodMasjoody), "Assuming (strongly) the accuracy of Mr. Foad Pashaei's narrative, Yasmin Pahlavi has been the cause and reason for the breakup and collapse of two noisy (albeit ultimately ineffective) opposition institutions in recent years: 'Solidarity' (according to @FoadPashaei) and Farashgard (as I witnessed firsthand)," Twitter, February 29, 2024

to use coercion and intimidation align the organization with Etemadi.¹²⁹ These revelations also cast Reza Pahlavi in a light of indecision and hesitancy in leadership, a portrayal corroborated by Kenneth R. Timmerman's "Countdown to Crisis" and insights from former advisors.¹³⁰

The Monarchist Bloc's discourse is notably less diversified compared to other political factions, with key figures controlling the frame narrative, more so than Pahlavi himself. Deviations from their stipulated discourse are often met with public denunciation and vilification.

The dissolution of Farashgard and its reconstitution as Farashgard Foundation and Iran Novin Party, led by defectors from the original group, did not signify a departure from its established discursive practices. This pattern of behavior resonates with several former constitutional monarchist activists and exponents of monarchism, including Masjoody, Ali Ashtari (another Farashgard founder), and other notable political figures.

5.2.3 Confederalist Bloc

Advocates for a confederalist structure, envisioning autonomous nation-states within Iran, often exhibit a propensity for violent reactions to ideological rifts, given their status as the primary armed factions in the Iranian opposition. The PDKI's four-year conflict with the Komala Organization of the Communist Party of Iran (KOCPI), which was previously supported by the Soviet Union, stemmed from accusations against the PDKI of being a "Class-enemy."¹³¹ In 2000, the Komala Party of Iranian Kurdistan (Komala) left the KOCPI, subsequently splitting into factions like the Komala of the Toilers of Kurdistan and the Komala Reformist branch.¹³²

The establishment of the Democratic Platform of Iranian People (Platform-e Democratic-e Khalqhay-e Iran), or the Democratic Platform of Iranian Nationalities, in 2018, under the political ideology of Democratic Confederalism promoted by Abdullah Ocalan and the Kurdistan Communities Union (KCK), linked to the Kurdistan Free Life Party (PJAK), did not achieve significant impact or recognition, especially within its intended audience in Iranian Kurdistan, following the WLF movement.

A common thread among these confederalist entities is their call for the acknowledgment of ethnic groups as distinct national entities, occasionally blurring the lines with demands for sovereign status, while simultaneously rejecting labels of "separatism" directed at them.

¹²⁹ Ibid.

¹³⁰ Ibid.

¹³¹ Franc Milburn, "Iranian Kurdish Militias: Terrorist-Insurgents, Ethno Freedom Fighters, or Knights on the Regional Chessboard?" CTC Sentinel 10, no. 5 (May 2017),

¹³² Ibid.

PDKI and Komala stand out as principal representatives not only of their immediate constituencies but also of the broader segment of the population advocating for federal governance based on ethnic considerations. However, this stance faces opposition from Azerbaijani confederalist groups, who contend that PDKI and PJAK activities in West Azerbaijan threaten the territorial unity of Azerbaijani confederalism within Iran.

The scale of infighting between confederalist members and the scale of contention among confederalist advocates is greater than either the monarchist or the republican blocs. This is because they hold the only armed opposition groups that challenge the state's monopoly on violence and lay claims to exclusive territories of their respective Sprachraum.

The Azerbaijani confederalists posit that the territories of the Azerbaijan province, and the provinces of Ardebil, Zanjan, Qazvin, Gilan, Hamedan, and Alborz, constitute the South Azerbaijan territories. This position is contested unanimously by all Kurdish confederalist groups, which claim portions of West Azerbaijan and Hamedan provinces as Kurdish territories, in addition to the provinces of Ilam, Kermanshah, Lorestan, and often as far south as the province on the coast of the Persian Gulf, Bushehr. The manifesto of PDKI asserts that Kurdish territories are defined by the areas where the Kurdish language is spoken. The vagueness, however, emerges in what constitutes the Kurdish language. Many pan-Kurdish activists consider Lur, Lak, Feyli, and languages spoken in the southwestern provinces as Kurdish.

The territories claimed by Kurdish parties partially overlap with territories claimed by Pan-Arab separatist movements, who are most comfortable being recognized as separatists instead of federalists. In the southeastern regions, Baloch confederalist organizations clash with pan-Islamic organizations over the claim to represent the true position of the Baloch population. The confederalists are also divided on the principles and policies they advocate. While certain organizations, such as the Balochistan People's Party, appeal to socialist values and focus on confederalism within Iran, others, such as Raji Tepaki, openly call for the creation of a Balochi nation-state with irredentist calls to reclaim the Sprachraum of the Baloch people.¹³³

5.2.4 Non-Partisan Bloc

The nonpartisan entities advocating for civil and fundamental human rights, alongside a collective transitional framework, have garnered substantial resonance among the public. Foremost among these

¹³³ "Raji Tepaki Gol's Constitution and Constitution of Balochistan Approved by the Second Congress of 1403," Party BNS, May 11, 2024

entities are the Iran Transitional Council (ITC), PS752 Association, and various human rights organizations.

The ITC has articulated a vision for transitioning from the IR, encapsulating a unification agenda for democratic forces, organizations, and political currents under the banner of freedom and democracy. The blueprint for field strategies and the formulation of combat methods are managed by the activists and leading members of social movements, positioning them at the forefront of the struggle.¹³⁴ Declared as a pluralistic body, the ITC amalgamates political, academic, and professional individuals, alongside representatives from diverse Iranian ethnicities and ideological backgrounds. It formally entered the political sphere on September 28 and 29, 2019, with its founding committee, emphasizing the urgency of forging a broad national alliance to steer organized protests and systematic, peaceful struggles towards the establishment of a democratic governance structure through free elections.

ITC membership hinges on adherence to five foundational principles: upholding Iran's national unity and territorial sovereignty, endorsing a parliamentary democracy that segregates religion from state affairs, committing to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and its treaties, advocating for the transition away from the Islamic regime, and combating all forms of discrimination.¹³⁵

The PS752 Association, initiated to represent the families of the 140 victims of the Ukrainian International Airlines Flight PS752 tragedy, has been pivotal in conducting investigative reports and spearheading large-scale demonstrations both within and outside Iran. Despite its president, Esmailiun, playing a crucial role in the Coalition Council and drafting the Mahsa Charter, the organization maintains its apolitical stance, focusing solely on protesting against the human rights violations of the IR, without projecting a preference for a post-IR polity.

The most considerably potent and influential group within the non-partisan bloc are social media influencers, celebrities and individuals independent of parties and political affiliation. They often garner greater amount of social media and discursive presence than veteran opposition political figures and communities with decades of experience in oppositionality. Non-organizational and manifestedly un-aligned activists with considerable social influence, such as Alinejad many others can be sorted in this bloc as well.

Through the last two sections, two arguments were established: Firstly, what discursive frame is posited by the WLF movement, and secondly, what are the frames of the discursive actors within the institution of oppositionality prior to the WLF protests. It has become evident that four decades of

¹³⁴ Iran Transitional Council, "Third Term Constitution of the Transition Management Council, Approved May 18, 2023,"

¹³⁵ Ibid.

oppositonality to the IR has not been sufficient for the opposition actors to consolidate their own political bloc, which is a logical prerequisite to forming a united opposition. It is now a debate whether the discursive juncture of the WLF movement introduced a brief period of solidarity to the opposition before the discourse reverted to its natural condition of fragmentation. In this interpretation, the failure of coalition building is the naturally extrapolated trajectory of Iranian oppositionality – not a puzzle. Instead, the puzzle is how the WLF movement galvanized a phase of solidarity amidst the historical discord of the opposition.

In response to these findings, the next chapter will empirically explore the discursive shift with delicate attention to the discursive developments of the opposition blocs during the 72 weeks of heightened protests.

6. Discord In Discourse

There are two primary spaces for discursive exchange between Iranian oppositional blocs: street demonstrations and the digital sphere. Internet restrictions within the country have significantly limited access to the digital space, with only a few platforms like WhatsApp and domestically developed chat applications being readily accessible. While platforms like Telegram are available through commonly used VPNs, access to X, ClubHouse, Reddit and similar “public square” applications require more expensive circumvention tools.

Yet, the constriction of these digital spaces has not entirely impeded the flow of discourse. Activities within these restricted areas often find their way onto more accessible platforms through screenshots shared on WhatsApp and Telegram, thereby creating secondary spaces for discursive exchange. Vice versa, screenshots from these platforms would also find their way back into the public square applications to generate more reactions and enable a sense of discursive exchange. This challenges the impression that discourses during the protest movement were confined to isolated digital environments.

In the preceding chapter, multiple typologies of the political opposition were delineated based on discursive activities within these secondary spaces on Telegram, employing Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), frame analysis, and empirical data from a sister study that utilized PEW method surveys to deconstruct the typologies of the opposition.

The examination of these Telegram channels revealed three recurrent discursive patterns: Universal solidarity (Solidarity), as a reflection for frame expansion, alignment, and openness to consensus building. In-group consolidation (Ingroup), is another reflection of competitive frame expansion when groups embolden the ideological and identity lines between their support base and nonpartisan groups. Out-group hostility (Outgroup) as a mechanism of competitive frame expansion and aggressive hegemonization of the discursive frame. This is not to be confused with agonistic pluralism which opposes Habermassian deliberative consensus building. The observed phenomenon is antithetical to any productive deliberation – it is a coordinated agonism for competition and hegemonization of the oppositionality discourse.

These patterns were exhibited variably across most of the typological groups, irrespective of their specific stances or ideologies. The investigation of these discursive shifts aimed to evaluate the theory that hostile discourse and resultant fragmentation are directly attributable to the in-group consolidation efforts amid the expansion of frames. This section is dedicated to demonstrating the testing of this

theory, by analyzing the relationship between the diminishing sense of solidarity and the rise of fragmentary discourse within the oppositional discursive institution.

6.1. Correlative Patterns

In the preceding chapter, eleven typologies of political opposition were delineated based on discursive activities within these secondary spaces on Telegram, employing CDA, frame analysis, and empirical data from a sister study that utilized PEW method surveys to deconstruct the typologies of the opposition.

After visualizing the discursive shift, Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed to assess the linear relationships between three key discursive patterns. These patterns were quantified as percentage representations of discourse occurrences over 72 weeks, providing a temporal dataset suitable for correlation analysis.

In Pearson's correlation coefficient, a value closer to 1 indicates a strong positive correlation, meaning that as one variable increases, the other variable also increases. A value closer to -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, where an increase in one variable corresponds to a decrease in the other. Lastly, a value around 0 suggests no linear correlation between the variables.

Between Solidarity and In-group discourse, the results show a correlation coefficient of -0.796 , suggesting a strong negative linear relationship, indicating that increases in solidarity discourse are associated with decreases in ingroup discourse.

The strong negative correlation between Solidarity and Ingroup discursive patterns suggests an inverse relationship wherein periods of heightened solidarity are likely to see a diminution in ingroup-focused discourse. This could reflect a discursive shift from parochial or bloc-centric frames towards more inclusive or collectivist themes driven by external events or internal compromises to build consensus. This would of course also provide a reverse effect which was posited by the given theories: In-group consolidation discourse has an adverse effect on solidarity discourse as a pretext for consensus building.

When assessing Solidarity against the Out-group the given coefficient is -0.569 indicating a moderate negative linear relationship, implying that higher expressions of solidarity are somewhat associated with lower expressions of outgroup discourse. A moderate negative correlation between Solidarity and Out-group patterns suggests that as solidarity expands focus on the outgroup hostility diminishes. Likewise, out-group hostility has a relatively smaller impact on the consensus-building effort. We may further infer that the fragmentation –as a failure of deliberative consensus– is not affected by out-group hostility, but rather the in-group consolidation.

Lastly, In-group and Out-group give us A near-zero coefficient of -0.044 . This reflects a negligible linear relationship, suggesting that changes in ingroup discourse have little to no linear association with changes in outgroup discourse. The negligible correlation between Ingroup and Outgroup discourses implies that these two dimensions of discourse operate independently within the political frames, suggesting that the internal dynamics of group identity and the external orientation towards outgroups are not strongly interconnected in linear terms. This independence could mean that In-group consolidation and hostility are part of the same broader political or social discourse.

The heatmap displays the correlation matrix for the discursive patterns "Solidarity," "Ingroup," and "Outgroup." Each cell shows the correlation coefficient between the patterns, with the color indicating the strength and direction of the relationship.

6.2. Identifying Discursive Trends

Time series analysis decomposes time series for each of the discursive patterns to understand underlying trends. Although the theory posited a linear shift in the discursive patterns, the obtained results demonstrate fluctuations and discursive complexities that necessitate an episodic assessment of discursive shift – which will be addressed in Chapter 7.

The analysis utilized the `seasonal_decompose` function from the `statsmodels` library to decompose time series into its constituent elements. In this method, we posit an additive model where the 72 weeks is the sum of the trend. The trend component represents long-term progression, the seasonal component captures systematic, calendar-related movements, and the residual component encompasses irregular fluctuations.

Solidarity discourse showed a general decline over the period, with the seasonal component indicating periodic fluctuations. The data confirms the observation of a decline in solidarity discourse. Ingroup discourse is posited with increasing trend, with the seasonal component reflecting less pronounced periodic fluctuations than Solidarity and more consistency throughout the 72 weeks. Lastly, The

Ougroup hostility discourse shows more variability compared to Solidarity and Ingroup, with more peaks and troughs.

The declining trend in Solidarity discourse and inclination in Ingroup discourse complements the theory on discursive shift being mechanized through frame expansion and frame consolidation strategies. However, the seasonal fluctuations indicate cyclical factors affecting solidarity, further necessitating an assessment of the the episodes behind the discursive shifts.

The increasing trend in Ingroup discourse also complements the first theory positing a strong emphasis on frame consolidation and competitive expansion – over consensus building. This is indicative of a strengthening of identity politics and in-group solidarity in response to external challenges.

The irregularities with hostile out-group discourse could signify changing attitudes towards outgroups during discursive episodes as external circumstances that require strategic recalibrations. Given the universality of this assumption and lack of correlation between In-group consolidation and outgroup hostility, the role of far-axial groups –as posited in the second theory– can be minimized or nullified.

The reliability of this inference is assessed with OLS regression. The regression model is aimed to yield coefficients representing the average change in discourse percentages per week, along with R-squared values indicating the proportion of variance explained by time – as the independent variable.

A negative coefficient was identified in solidarity discourse, indicating a statistically significant decrease in solidarity discourse over time. The model's R-squared value suggested that a substantial proportion of the variance in Solidarity could be explained by the temporal dimension. The Ingroup consolidation discourse demonstrated a positive coefficient, translating to a significant increase in this discursive pattern as time progressed. The R-squared value indicated that time accounted for a considerable amount of the variation in Ingroup discourse. Likewise, the out-group hostility discourse shows positive coefficient for Outgroup implied a slight, yet statistically significant, upward trend over the period. However, the data suggests this trend is less pronounced and potentially influenced by a wider range of variables not captured in the linear model.

	R-Squared	Coefficient for time	P-Value
Solidarity	0.522	1.0589	< 0.0001
Ingroup	0.497	0.8256	< 0.0001
Outgroup	0.109	0.2928	0.005

6.3. Identifying the Episodes

To identify the discursive disruptions for an episodic discursive assessment, Change Point Detection was utilized. This method doesn't have a concrete methodical approach besides its key objective being the identification of pattern deviations. Two out-of-convention methods considered for this approach were integration of rolling mean in Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test. ADF is used to determine if a time series is stationary or contains a unit root, which is a characteristic of time series that show trends or seasonality, which was explored in the preceding section. The rolling mean involved calculating the average of the data points within a moving window over the time series. Given a separate dataset was created for each week by each typological group, the rolling mean method was the only appropriate approach to identifying the discursive episodes. This method smoothed out short-term fluctuations and highlighted longer-term trends or cycles.

The analysis identified several weeks where substantial changes in the discourse were observed:

- **Solidarity:** Weeks 21, 26, 31-34, 55-56, 58, 60, 61, 63, and 70
- **Ingroup:** Weeks 20, 38, 52, 54, 61, 63, 69-70, and 72
- **Outgroup:** Weeks 31-34, 37, 49, 51, and 54

Common weeks identified across the three discursive patterns were around weeks 31-34, 61, and 63, suggesting there were substantial changes or disruptions that affected the discourse. These identified focal points will be assessed as discursive episodes in Chapter 7.

In a brief conclusion, the empirical findings from the first three sections of this chapter lend support to the first theory: That opposition groups initially engaged in a solidarity discourse, which rapidly waned as in-group consolidation discourse emerged. This shift implies that the original solidarity discourse was perhaps superficially maintained, with each group primarily focused on amplifying their own discursive frames under the facade of unity.

The third theoretical proposition, which links hostile discourse to fragmentation as a consequence of in-group consolidation efforts, warrants reconsideration. The empirical data suggest a limited correlation between solidarity discourse and in-group consolidation with out-group hostility discourses. To refine this theory, it is proposed that in-group consolidation is a strategic maneuver aimed at dominating the oppositionality frame. This refined theory aligns with Porta's contention that consensus-building contrasts with the exhibition of power and discursive intimidation used to dominate discourse. Consequently, out-group hostility may not constitute an independent discursive pattern but rather serves as a mechanism to reinforce in-group consolidation by intimidating other opposition factions.

Moreover, the data challenge the idea of a gradual and consistent shift in discursive patterns. Although trends in in-group consolidation and solidarity discourses are discernible, the cyclicity and seasonality of these trends point to their substantial shaping by episodic shifts. This cyclic nature will be scrutinized further in subsequent analyses. However, to set the stage for this exploration, it is crucial to comprehend the instances of solidarity discourse and the ensuing in-group consolidations, which are bolstered by both in-group discourse and out-group hostility mechanisms. This understanding will provide a necessary foundation to contextualize the episodic shifts that will be examined in greater detail in the forthcoming chapter.

6.4. Universal Solidarity

The data highlights the significant role of solidarity discourse during the initial stages of the WLF protests. By early October, numerous political and non-political organizations surfaced, each claiming to spearhead the formation of a united front against the IR, representing the collective opposition. However, these declarations of intent were predominantly confined to the signing of memorandums or letters that professed a shared goal of establishing a united front, while continuing to preserve their distinct discursive identities.

In response to the evolving dynamics of the protests, existing groups and institutions with significant influence realigned their frames and strategies to accommodate the unfolding uncertainties.

Among the entities that surfaced at the movement's onset was the People Foundation (Bonyad-e Mardom), endorsed by prominent Iranian figures like cartoonist Mana Neyestani and actress Golshifteh Farahani.¹³⁶ The foundation claimed to be the inaugural body to undertake the mission for research on pivotal issues shaping Iran's political and social future amidst the early months of the WLF protests.

Furthermore, several catch-all coalitions rose from within the monarchist bloc. A notable "Oath of cooperation" was initiated between the largest monarchist political party, Mashruteh, the Iran Transitional Council (ITC), and the National Council of Decision (Shoray-e Melli-e Tasmin), also known as Tasmin. The agreement proclaimed that the WLF revolution heralded a new epoch in Iran's storied history.¹³⁷ It underscored the pivotal roles of key groups within the movement, lauding the women, youth, and students, among other societal segments, for setting a remarkable precedent of non-violent civil resistance.¹³⁸ It posited that this movement has gained international acclaim, extending beyond Iran's borders, with the collective aspiration to liberate Iran from theocratic domination towards a regime characterized by rule of law, freedom, and popular sovereignty.¹³⁹

The group acknowledged the disarray within the opposition, emphasizing the necessity of a coherent and robust opposition that genuinely embodies the revolution's essence and champions the populace's legitimate aspirations. It contended that establishing such a framework is imperative to curtail the fragmentation among authentic democratic entities, fostering unity against the despotic regime of the

¹³⁶ Mardom Foundation, "General Objectives of the Organization," Mardom Foundation, accessed May 15, 2024,

¹³⁷ Constitutional Party of Iran, "Cooperation Pact" (Constitutional Party of Iran, February 23, 2023).

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Ibid.

IR. This, they argued, would pave the way for a democratic transition and significantly impact the alteration of existing power structures.¹⁴⁰

In its blueprint for a coalition, the group delineated specific criteria for participation. The text articulated: “The Constitutional Party of Iran (Liberal Democrat), the TIS, and the Tasmin are dedicated to fostering collaboration and unity to establish an extensive democratic coalition [...] fundamental tenets for this alliance include 1. commitment to Iran's territorial unity and national solidarity, 2. endorsement of a secular democratic transition, 3. compliance with international human rights standards, 4. eradication of discrimination, 5. decentralization in national governance, and 6. deciding the future political framework through a democratic referendum.”¹⁴¹

The declaration concluded with a salutation: “Long live the Women-Life-Freedom revolution and national solidarity for saving Iran.”¹⁴² The trope to align the WLF revolution with a nationalist zeal for the liberation of Iran and establishing popular sovereignty became common for the other polities that emerged in the subsequent months. Despite being initiated by well-recognized entities within the legacy opposition, this coalition did not capture significant attention from the diaspora's mainstream media platforms.

Contrastingly, the coalition named Seventh Aban Front (7Aban), established by a few recognizable names and no grassroots support in Iran, garnered more focus from the mainstream opposition media.¹⁴³ The original foundational document of 7Aban, which has been modified in the version currently accessible on their website, began with the declaration that the national revolution, under the “Woman, Life, Freedom” slogan, is destined to liberate Iran from the clutches of the Islamic theocracy, ushering in a new, hopeful era globally. It reiterates the centrality of women's leadership in the movement, supported by the brave men of Iran, envisioning a future where freedom, prosperity, and the eradication of oppression and discrimination prevail.¹⁴⁴

The mission statement of the group, distinct from the Oath of Cooperation, aimed to embody the spirit of the Iranian national revolution and secure international backing for it. The objectives included isolating the Islamic regime and its allies globally, recognizing and addressing the necessities of domestic resistance forces, cooperating with all democratic factions to ensure the revolution's success,

¹⁴⁰ Ibid.

¹⁴¹ Ibid.

¹⁴² Ibid.

¹⁴³ Seven Aban Front, “Fundamental Statement of Solidarity for the Freedom of Iran,” Seven Aban Front, October 29, 2022

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

maintaining national stability and security, and protecting the rights and fundamental freedoms of the Iranian populace post the IR's collapse.¹⁴⁵

Unlike the Oath of Cooperation, there were no explicit strategies outlined for collaboration with this group. The statement further delineated key principles guiding the group's activities: establishing a liberal democracy, fostering national unity and territorial integrity, determining the future democratic framework through a referendum, secularism, and adhering to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The proclamation of these principles was marked by the founding members reciting “Jin Jian Azadi,” echoing the chants from Saqqez during Mahsa Jina Amini's burial. In the current version of the statement, “Jin Jian Azadi” has been replaced with its Persian equivalent “Zan Zendegi Azadi.”¹⁴⁶ This, I reckon to be in the aftermath of the attempt to divorce the WLF movement from its Kurdish influence, which to the zealot nationalists was projected as a trojan ploy to introduce democratic confederalism in Iran.

The restrictive conditions for collaboration set by these groups, in theory, did not preclude members of the Confederalist bloc from participating. Previous discussions highlighted that entities like PDKI and Komala have committed to pursuing their political objectives within Iran's recognized bound territories and have actively sought to dissociate the notion of separatism from their confederalist governance model, as propagated by the IR to legitimize its aggression towards these groups.

However, a significant factor contributing to 7Aban's lack of widespread support can be attributed to the background of its founding members. Among them, Saeed Bashirtash, the spouse of Darya Safai, a Belgian MP from the N-VA party, stood out. Despite Safai's political acumen and connections, including with Alinejad, Bashirtash's relatively unknown status and his associations, notably with Peyman Aref, a journalist with ties to the IR, cast doubts on his motives. Bashirtash lack any political experience while claiming to have membership in the Nation Party of Iran (NPI),¹⁴⁷ an organization known for its opposition to capitalism, communism, monarchism, anti-Semitism, Bahá'ism, and for adopting a Nazi insignia as its flag.¹⁴⁸

The mission of 7Aban diverged from the Oath of Cooperation, aiming to embody the essence of the Iranian national revolution and solicit international support, thereby isolating the Islamic regime and its

¹⁴⁵ Ibid.

¹⁴⁶ Ibid.

¹⁴⁷ Saeed Bashirtash, "About Me," Bashirtash.org

¹⁴⁸ Masoud Kazemzadeh, "Opposition groups," in *Iran Today: An Encyclopedia of Life in the Islamic Republic*, eds. Mehran Kamrava and Manochehr Dorraj, vol. 2 (Westport, CT: Greenwood Press, 2008), 364.

associates. This mission entailed identifying and addressing the necessities of domestic activists, fostering collaboration with all democratic entities to ensure the revolution's success, and upholding the stability, security, and fundamental freedoms of the Iranian populace after the IR's downfall. Unlike the Oath of Cooperation, 7Aban's approach lacked explicit mechanisms for collaboration.

Their proclamation stipulated key guiding principles for their activities: the establishment of a liberal democracy, national unity, territorial integrity, determining the political future through a referendum, the separation of religion and state, and adherence to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. This declaration, marked by the echoing chants of “Jin Jian Azadi,” mirrored the sentiments expressed in Saqqez at Mahsa Jina Amini’s funeral. Subsequent revisions saw the removal of “Jin Jian Azadi” from the statement, replaced with its Persian translation “Zan Zendegi Azadi.”

Despite setting these exclusive conditions for partnership, such stipulations did not preclude members of the Confederalist bloc from potential collaboration. As highlighted earlier, entities like PDKI and Komala have consistently emphasized their political aspirations within Iran’s territorial confines, vehemently distinguishing their confederalist governance model from separatism, a narrative propagated by the IR to legitimize its aggression against these groups.

7Aban's struggle to mobilize support is partly attributed to the background of its founding figures, such as Saeed Bashirtash. Despite potential leverage through connections with figures like Darya Safai, Bashirtash's credibility was undermined by his lack of recognition and controversial affiliations, notably his history with the politically ambiguous Nation Party of Iran and its extremist ideologies. The background of the other founding members of 7Aban also exemplified the organization's right-leaning ideological inclination. This alignment was evident in the group's efforts to project their bloc’s narrative as a form of universal solidarity, consistent with the initially manifested proposition.

On the left of the spectrum, United4Mahsa emerged as a structured entity, vocalizing not just opposition to compulsory Hijab but also advocating for liberation from theocratic governance. They underscored the particularly personal nature of this struggle for Iranian women, framed within a broader feminist revolution, underscoring the universal appeal of their cause.¹⁴⁹

In the diaspora, a significant coalition statement from the left-leaning and confederalist factions materialized in October 2022, culminating in a major demonstration in Berlin.¹⁵⁰ This coalition,

¹⁴⁹ United4Mahsa, "About Us," United4Mahsa

¹⁵⁰ Etehad-e-Fadayan, "With the Slogan Woman, Life, Freedom – Join the Nationwide Protests in Berlin / Four Political Coalitions," Union of People's Fadaian of Iran, October 19, 2022

comprising various Federalist and Confederalist groups, demonstrated a novel and emergence of a new wave of solidarity among a historically divided bloc.

The proclamations from left-leaning entities like Hamgami also emphasized solidarity with the national endeavors and protests in Iran, addressing the "Woman, Life, Freedom" as slogan of the liberation struggle.¹⁵¹ Their call for participation rallies not only democratic, republican, leftist, and socialist factions but also individuals advocating for freedom, democracy, and equality, aiming for an Iran liberated from the IR's clutches.¹⁵² Hamgami's formation, intriguingly predating the WLF movement. Their frame alignment strategy to the emergence of the movement is best interpreted as frame transformation.

In fact, this became a recurring pattern between all emergin coalition projects. Regardless of the political orientation and alignments, there were different degrees of frame transformation at tht onset of the movement in an attempt to align all political and mobilization efforts with the WLF uprising. The frame narrative of all emergin coalitions emphasized the role of women and youth at the forefront, while advocating for a transformative shift from the IR to a democratic and secular governance. To a degree we henceforth can affair the first theory to correspond to the observations. The dominant emerging coalitions rooted in legacy opposition groups responded to the WLF's discursive juncture, by aligning their discursive frame with the movement.

While thes solidarity-building coalitions all simultaneously aligned with the broader revolutionary ethos, encapsulating themes of democracy, secularism, and the pivotal role of women, their *legacy* status begets a form of exclusionary discourse. This does not necessarily translate to their objective to hegemonize the narrative. With the case of Hamgami's released statement, it exclusively addresses the republican aspiration to exclude the non-republican factions from consensus deliberation.

The assertion that that legacy coalitions enveloped their internal discourse within a veneer of national solidarity is overly simplistic and misleading. It's demonstrably clear, particularly among the legacy left-oriented groups, that they averted adopting a universal solidarity framework. Their hesitance to broaden their consensus-building to include non-aligned blocs, is debatable a influential factor in their diminished presence and recognition within the Iranian populace – as evidenced by their scant social media engagement and the surprisingly low representation in Gamaan's 2022 survey data.¹⁵³

¹⁵¹ Hamgami. "Announcement of the Formation of 'Hamgami for Secular Democratic Republic in Iran'." Hamgami, March 9, 2023.

¹⁵² Ibid.

¹⁵³ Gamaan, 2022

Despite survey results indicating a substantial segment of Iranians favoring a secular republic (33.6%), a federal structure (11.7%), and a preference for a social democratic party (20.2%), the inability of legacy left parties to resonate with these preferences suggests a significant disconnect.¹⁵⁴ This disconnect seemingly leaves a vast swath of the population without a representative voice that aligns with their aspirations for universal solidarity.

There exists a great representational vacuum for the Republican discourse. Those politically apathetic, marginalized by non-republican groups, or those with fluctuating political inclination could also fit within this vacuum which is colloquially called the Grey Society (Qeshr-e Khakestari). Many in this vacuum could find resonance not with parties, but to recognized individuals. Esmailiun, leading the PS752 Association, has risen as a figure of representing the interests of certain non-confederalists and non-monarchists in the popular discourse. A role that is also shared with Alinejad. This is indeed strongly aligned with the global emergence of celebrity politics to the development of mainstream politics.

Meanwhile, those skeptical of ethnic confederalism while advocating for provincial federalism or social democratic framework found Mohtadi of the Komala party as a palatable compromise. Media units covering debates and discourses over forms of governance, including federalism, played a key role in pulling the subject out of the discursive taboos of the legacy opposition.

The zenith of the solidarity ethos and opposition's popularity, and as many have argued, was achieved with a synchronized social media posts on the 2023 New Year's Eve. Prominent opposition figures, Pahlavi, Alinejad, Ebadi, Esmailiun and others shared a post calling for unity and coalition building. This kindled a renewed sense of possibility for a cohesive opposition among many Iranians.¹⁵⁵

The anticipation stirred by the post hinted at the emergence of an extensive solidarity initiative, the Alliance for Democracy and Freedom in Iran. The coalition initially included Pahlavi, Alinejad, Mohtadi, Esmailiun, Karimi, the actresses Farahani and Boniadi, and nobel laureate lawyer, Ebadi. This coalition was seen as one of the most formidable challenge to the IR in its four-decade history.¹⁵⁶ Although the specifics of the MAHSA Charter are addressed here, the prelude to its establishment will be detailed in the subsequent chapter.

The MAHSA Charter, steeped in a narrative of universal solidarity, opens with a collective acknowledgment of the wounds inflicted by the IR, proposing that the path to a liberated and

¹⁵⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵⁵ Iran International, "Prince Reza Pahlavi and Some Opposition Figures Release a Joint New Year's Message," Iran International, December 31, 2022,

¹⁵⁶ Ibid.

democratic Iran necessitates surmounting the current regime. Notably, the charter abstains from ideological bias, instead establishing fundamental values and conditions for collaboration. Its democratic ethos is highlighted by advocating for a referendum to ascertain the governance model, alongside commitments to secular democracy, national unity, decentralized power, the establishment of an electoral ombudsman, and the pursuit of democratic elections.¹⁵⁷

Comprising 17 clauses, the charter predominantly assures foreign entities of the democratic dedication of its signatories, facilitating discussions to aid Iranian protesters and strike actions.¹⁵⁸ This instance could be seen as diverging from the argument that solidarity discourse often masks a motive to promote a specific political agenda.

Yet, the solidarity wave began to wane as it was affected by growing internal discord and alleged hidden clandestine agendas to politicize the movement, including accusations of promoting ethnic balkanization of Iran, endorsing undemocratic ideals, perpetuating ethno-centric biases, and commandeering the cause as a feminist crusade. All allegations exclusively pushed by the royalist bloc of the monarchists and the Islamic Republic affiliated journalists.

Post the dissolution of the Coalition Council, further entities surfaced under the banner of solidarity. Yet, public skepticism towards unfamiliar or controversial figures stymied the formation of a unified front. The PS752 Association's role in establishing the Aban Families For Justice—a solidarity coalition for the families affected by the 2019 crackdown—was significant. Despite the group's backing by victim families, its association with the PS752 Association and its president Esmailiun attracted vehement criticism and slander, particularly from royalists opposed to Esmailiun.

¹⁵⁷ ADFI, "The Mahsa Charter: Charter of Solidarity and Alliance for Freedom" (ADFI, March 9, 2023)

¹⁵⁸ Ibid.

6.5. In-Group Consolidation

The second theory of this research posited the competitive frame alignment impeded dialogical consensus building with other opposition blocs, leading to a hostile discursive turn within the opposition. The discussion in this chapter aims to explore this theory based on the conclusion that was contrived in chapter 6.1 – where outgroup hostility and ingroup consolidation were, to differing degrees, of the same stem.

The concept of in-group consolidation is understood as a preference for extending and consolidating a competitive frame over pursuing consensus-building dialogue. This is founded on the discussion from Chapter 4.3.3. The empirical data support this observation, notably in the actions of entities like 7Aban, United4Mahsa, and many left-leaning legacy parties. The goal of in-group consolidation is to foster a semblance of unity within a singular political frame, achieved through narratives of internal unity or external hostility.

Instances of in-group consolidation were evident even before the Mahsa Charter's unveiling, with syndicate guilds across various sectors like education, healthcare, and labor seeking to forge a unified front for enhanced coordination.

A pivotal moment that underscored in-group consolidation –or the monopolization of opposition discourse– was an interview featuring Pahlavi on the monarchist media, Manoto.¹⁵⁹ The interviewer questions Pahlavi on the possibility of coalition-building, probing his stance on collaborating with federalists, whom she deliberately labels as separatists who do not recognize Iran's territorial integrity. While Pahlavi had previously distinguished between federalism and separatism, engaging with groups like PDKI and Komala and even acknowledging the autonomy demands for Kurdistan,¹⁶⁰ in this interview, he denied willingness to ally with those that do not recognize the territorial integrity. Although a common sense at first, his failure to clear whether he believes federalists are included in this cluster provoked a reaction from federalist advocates.

He reiterated four conditions aligning with those in the Oath of Cooperation: respect for territorial integrity, commitment to secular democracy, adherence to human rights, and determining the governance model through a referendum.¹⁶¹ Furthermore, Pahlavi articulated a need for confirmatory representationalism to effectively garner international support and exert pressure on the IR, highlighting the strategic considerations within in-group consolidation efforts.

¹⁵⁹ Manoto TV, "Special Newsroom Interview with Prince Reza Pahlavi," YouTube video, January 16, 2023

¹⁶⁰ Ibid.

¹⁶¹ Ibid.

The aftermath of Pahlavi's interview with Manoto resurrected the deep-seated divisions within the opposition, particularly among leftist groups who perceived Pahlavi's references to "separatism" and "territorial integrity" as pretexts for perpetuating the IR's oppressive tactics against ethnic interest advocates. This was merely one of the instances from which in-group consolidation discourse shifted the mainstream discourse from dialogues aimed at strengthening internal unity to outward antagonism.

The 7Aban group's response to the Mahsa Charter exemplified this trend. In a statement released on March 11, 7Aban criticized the charter for neglecting national unity and the solidarity of the Iranian nation, noting the conspicuous absence of terms like "nation of Iran"¹⁶² and the lack of emphasis on "territorial integrity." It must be noted a separate clause was indeed given to the importance of territorial integrity. However, disinformation mechanism had become a formative toolkit of the royalist opposition groups. The group expressed concerns that the charter conditionally acknowledged Iran's territorial integrity, a stance they found troubling and unacceptable.¹⁶³

7Aban's critique extended to what they perceived as the charter's foundation on a vision for a new, ahistorical nation, devoid of a collective past.¹⁶⁴ They lamented the charter's focus on foreign negotiations, which they argued lacked a clear strategy for regime change. The statement from 7Aban also took issue with the use of "ethnic" terminology and Marxist influences, advocating instead for discussions centered on geographical advantages and environmental justice.¹⁶⁵

The group's apprehension about being marginalized or overshadowed by a larger, potentially hegemonic coalition was palpable in their statement, indicating a broader fear within the opposition of being eclipsed or excluded from significant collaborative efforts.

This anxiety was echoed in leaked audio from a meeting led by Mohtadi with Komala members, which revealed deliberate semantic choices in the writing of the charter aimed at fostering inclusivity, such as avoiding the role of "Persian language" as the lingua franca and preferring "people" over "nation" to accommodate federalist sensibilities.¹⁶⁶ These revelations highlighted the nuanced and often contentious efforts to balance nationalist and federalist interests within the opposition's discourse, underscoring the delicate attempt of coalition-building and identity politics in shaping Iran's oppositional narrative.

¹⁶² Seventh Aban Front, "Analytical Statement of the Seventh of Aban Front on the Charter of Solidarity" (Seven Aban Front, March 11, 2023).

¹⁶³ Ibid.

¹⁶⁴ Ibid.

¹⁶⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶⁶ Peyman Aref, "Audio File of Abdollah Mohtadi: All the Schemes of an Iran-Hating Mind!" YouTube video, September 16, 2023,

The recurrence of attempts by coalition members to impose their personal political agendas under the guise of universal solidarity was notably evident. The upcoming chapter will delve into how figures like Pahlavi and Alinejad, to varying degrees, sought to imprint their distinct political narratives onto the charter's ostensibly inclusive ethos although it was revealed that the initial draft was prepared by Esmailiun in active communication with Iran-based activists.¹⁶⁷

Hojjat Kalashi, a senior figure in the Pan-Iranist party and founder of the Constitutionalist Organization (Sazman-e Mashruteh/CO), emerged as a staunch opponent of the charter, condemning it as a roadmap for Iran's Balkanization and tarnishing Iranian history by allowing a leader from what he termed a terrorist organization, referring to Komala, to contribute significantly.

Echoing Kalashi's sentiments, other nationalist entities, including the Iran Novin Party (INP), originating from Farashgard's selective remnants, lambasted the charter. INP went further, persistently labeling the charter as undemocratic for advocating an electoral process across all political echelons. They contended that the revolution commenced with the Cyrus The Great Revolt in 2015, positioning the WLF movement as a continuation of this historical trajectory. Furthermore, INP pejoratively branded the WLF as mere riots, maligning its advocates as a resurgence of the condemned 1979 alliance between the Red and Black factions. Many members of the INP began circulating the label of *Disintegration Charter (Manshur Gosastegi)* referring to the impression that the Mahsa Charter was destined to disintegrate Iran.

These critiques lend credence to the hypothesis that certain legacy opposition entities, particularly from the right, manipulated the solidarity discourse to perpetuate their political ideologies. The findings also suggest that the competitive frame expansion, hypothesized to hegemonize intra-bloc interactions and hinder dialogical consensus among opposition factions, requires reevaluation. While competitive expansion was observable, it was not the sole or direct impediment to consensus-building; rather, the reluctance or strategic refusal of certain groups and individuals to engage in deliberative processes played a more critical role.

This behavior was particularly manifest in left-leaning coalitions that structured their collaborative efforts to exclude non-leftist entities and in politically motivated organizations like INP, which utilized out-group hostility to solidify internal cohesion and deter deviation.

The third theory, which posits that the hostile discourse was the byproduct of in-group consolidation efforts during frame alignment to hegemonize the discourse over the WLF movement, cannot be nullified nor confirmed through these findings. However, if we interpret the creation of Coalition

¹⁶⁷ Karim Sadjadpour, 2024

Council, by the most recognized members of the opposition, as an inadvertant attempt to hegemonize or otherwise consolidate a united opposition with notable exclusion of th far-right groups, we reach the following adjusted theory: Hostile discourse is a byproduct of in-group consolidation efforts in *reaction* to the exclusionary hegemonization of the movement.

The rejected of the dominant narratives of the WLF movement, disinformation, strawman and the myriad tactics adopted by the far-right royalists to dislodge the emergence of a consolidated opposition also demands further exploration of the fourth theory: Failure in frame alignment is a deliberation by legacy opposition groups favoring the status quo over deliberative consensus-building and agonistic pluralism.

7. Episodic Phenomenology

Throughout the empirical chapters of this study, several critical episodes that significantly influenced the discursive patterns of the WLF protests have been identified. In chapter four, the emergence of competitive frames between the left and right factions was observed, particularly during the October 2nd protests where Yasmin Pahlavi became a focal point for contrasting discursive streams. The question then arises: what developments followed this event? Chapter six proposes that the discourse of solidarity experienced seasonal fluctuations, indicating that fractures in discourse at certain points were repaired at others.

Further inquiry is needed into how the founders of the Coalition Council reacted to their critics, and what were the key episodes leading to the coalition's eventual fragmentation and the events that followed. These questions are essential for a comprehensive episodic examination of the WLF protests, aiming to understand the motivations and strategic preferences of the actors involved, based on their historical actions and affiliations.

This research will particularly focus on weeks 21, 26, 31-34, 55-56, 58, 60, 61, 63, and 70 to analyze shifts in solidarity discourse. Similarly, weeks 20, 38, 52, 54, 61, 63, 69-70, and 72 will be examined for in-group consolidation discourse, and weeks 31-34, 37, 49, 51, and 54 for shifts in out-group hostility discourse. The overlapping weeks, particularly 31-34, 61, and 63, indicate significant episodes that likely had a profound impact on the discursive landscape.

The forthcoming sections aim to provide a detailed narrative of the events and dynamics that led to the transition from a unified discourse to one characterized by fragmentation.

7.1. Days After Mahsa

The sequence of events following Mahsa Jina Amini's death on September 16, 2022, served as a catalyst for widespread protests across the nation. In the immediate aftermath, the response was characterized by the tragic loss of young lives, with many girls and boys killed, arrested, or reported missing, their names circulating across social media platforms. This period saw a surge in the use of collaborative live spaces such as Twitter (later X), Instagram Lives, Clubhouse, and Telegram live sessions, creating a discursive field for Iranians to engage and share information.

The news of deaths, kidnappings, and mutilations spread rapidly through these channels, fueling increased protest activities nationwide. By September 23, Esmailiun, representing the PS750 Association, called for a gathering in Toronto, Canada, marking the first organized international protest, which, although small, set the stage for a larger event on October 1. This period was marked by escalating tensions and the early crystallization of the solidarity discourse within the protest movement.

Key developments in the third week intensified the situation. In response to the "Jin Jian Azadi" cries originating from Saqqez, Kurdistan province, the IR initiated bombings on PJAK positions in the Kurdish Regional Government of Iraq, attempting to portray Kurdish participation in the protests as separatist. Notably, PJAK's occasional strategic cooperation with the IRGC starkly contrasted with the consistent oppositionalism of Komala and PDKI and their hesitancy to negotiate for ceasefires.

The situation reached a critical point on September 30, during Friday prayers in Zahedan, Sistan, and Balochistan province, which escalated into violence when protesters reportedly attacked a militarized position in solidarity with the WLF protests. This incident, where the IR responded with live ammunition against protesters, was extensively covered on social media and other collaborative platforms, drawing significant attention to the ongoing Friday protests in the region. This day, September 30, would be remembered by Iranian protesters as the Bloody Friday of Zahedan and Khash, given the severity of the state's response to the protest on the peripheries.

A day after this tragic event, an unprecedented protest in Ontario, Canada, marked a turning point, drawing 50,000 participants to voice their outrage over Mahsa Jina Amini's death and the subsequent harsh measures by the IR. This large-scale demonstration accomplished two major outcomes: It pressured the international community to acknowledge the protests and consider dialogues with Iranian opposition figures, and it propelled Esmailiun, initially a lesser-known activist, into a prominent

political figure adept at mobilizing public support. His social media presence notably surged, gaining over a million followers in a week, as a testament to his growing influence.

Simultaneously, within Iran, a distressing event unfolded at Sharif University of Tehran, where IRGC forces besieged the university campus, leading to students being pursued and shot at. This incident sparked widespread calls for solidarity, notably from public figures like Karimi, urging people to rally in support of the students. The subsequent public outcry surrounding the university signaled a pivotal moment of collective action and unity for the emerging student syndicate movements.

This period saw the emergence of coordinated efforts among students and other societal sectors, further solidified when the regime's forces attacked Shahid High School in Ardebil, catalyzing stronger ties across civil society for organized resistance. The rapid succession of these events and the regime's intensifying crackdown during this early stage of the protests significantly bolstered the solidarity discourse, overshadowing the potential divisive incident in France involving Yasmin Pahlavi. This internal conflict within the opposition seemed to be momentarily eclipsed by the larger movement's momentum.

In the fifth week of the protest, another key episode took place: Evin Prison, which was the largest containment of prisoners of conscience, caught aflame, with rumors emerging that this was another “Cinema Rex incident”¹⁶⁸ with the IR deliberately attempting to kill Iranian prisoners. Once again, affirming the solidarity discourse, Iranians from across the country came out in protests. In Tehran, Iranians gathered around Evin Prison, creating an artificial jam around the compound to restrict the mobility of law enforcement vehicles trying to reach the area.

In the subsequent week, the Iranian diaspora achieved its greatest feat by organizing an event twice the size of the Ontario gathering. Promoted initially by the PS750 Association and endorsed by all key opposition figures, the Berlin gathering took place on October 22¹⁶⁹. The event received extensive praise and appreciation from across Iran and abroad, fixing the attention of policymakers on the Iran issue by converging the Ukraine-specific interests with the Iranian ones. On another front, the Berlin gathering also witnessed the second significant recorded incident where politically charged frames collided with the impression of attempting to hegemonize the movement. On several occasions, Iranian

¹⁶⁸ The Cinema Rex fire occurred on August 19, 1978, in Abadan, Iran. During a screening, the cinema was set ablaze, leading to the deaths of approximately 420 people, making it one of the deadliest terrorist attacks in history. The incident intensified the anti-Shah sentiment, contributing to the Iranian Revolution. While the Shah's government blamed Islamist militants, opposition groups accused SAVAK, the Shah's secret police, of orchestrating the tragedy to discredit the opposition. The true perpetrators remain unidentified, and the incident remains a significant and tragic event in Iranian history.

¹⁶⁹BBC News, "Iran Protests: Huge Rally in Berlin in Support," BBC News, October 23

leftist organizers restricted the access of Iranians carrying a Lion and Sun flag to the marching route, citing that the event was “not political” and that the Lion and Sun flag is a monarchist symbol.¹⁷⁰

This gatekeeping of oppositionality and protest movements, backed by restrictions on carrying the Lion and Sun flag, reverberated in Monarchist discursive forums and spaces for weeks afterward, all of whom blamed Esmailiun for the incident. He was seen as the figure who restricted the national symbolism and nationalist discourse to appease the “left,” despite the fact that the Lion and Sun flag was carried by demonstrators along with other flags.

The Berlin March remained the hallmark of the diaspora, showing committed solidarity with the cause at home. However, in the subsequent weeks, discourse in various spaces repeatedly found listeners and speakers divided on the realities that took place in Berlin.¹⁷¹ Old Facebook and blog posts of Esmailiun were pulled from the archives, demonstrating that, prior to losing his wife and child on the PS750 flight, Esmailiun had supported the Islamic Republic's institutions. This was also later evident in his reluctance to establish any strong connections with Pahlavi, despite Pahlavi's appeals to Esmailiun on several occasions.

Remnants of Farashgard members had already sown the seeds of division among the opposition by drawing ideological and generational borders that isolated dialogic consensus. They now began to operationalize this divide to galvanize the royalist monarchists in relentlessly delegitimizing Esmailiun's oppositionality and minimizing the significant achievement of the Berlin Gathering. Simultaneously, a video emerged from the premiere of a documentary Esmailiun had produced about PS750. Although Pahlavi had attended this event with his partner, Esmailiun allegedly neglected to recognize or greet Pahlavi, further angering the royalists. Yasmine Pahlavi later took to her social media to complain about this incident to her base of supporters.

Despite these internal conflicts, since the early weeks of the protest movements, the presence of solidarity discourse was maximized in the mainstream opposition discourse, and such incidents did not hamper the solidarity discourse of the general public.

In the seventh week of the protests, Mahsa's 40th-day anniversary was mourned across the country through escalated protests with slogans that had taken a more violent turn. Emboldened by the weaknesses demonstrated in the security forces and law enforcement, the subsequent week, on the 40th anniversary of Hadis Najafi, another young girl killed during the protests, one of the largest demonstrations took place in Iran's second-largest city, Karaj. This protest was accompanied by a

¹⁷⁰Ibid.

¹⁷¹Ibid.

galvanized crowd of angry protesters, resulting in violent clashes between security forces and the people. As a result of these clashes, several security forces were killed along with a larger number of protesters. The discourse of retribution as justice and threatening the security forces with retribution was manifested in action. By this point, as noted in the last chapter, the solidarity discourse occupied between 70% to 90% of the selected discourse patterns consistently throughout nearly ten weeks.

Reflective of Moaddel's thesis that the behavior of the opposition is shaped by the behavior of the IR, one could argue that the repressive mechanisms used to quell the protests during the subsequent episodes of the critical juncture that catalyzed the protests resulted in a consistent discourse of unity, maintaining cohesion among the opposition groups despite numerous discursive clashes during public demonstrations. The framings projected by the IR opposition groups were minimized in the presence of the frame emerging domestically in response to the IR's repressive crackdowns.

In the subsequent weeks, more violent clashes ensued with every Friday prayer event in Zahedan, followed by a disturbing number of Balochi citizens being arrested, injured, or killed by the security forces. On November 16, during the market strikes in Izeh, the security forces of the IRGC opened fire on a passenger vehicle, killing a 9-year-old boy named Kian Pirfalak. In fear of the security forces snatching her son's body, Kian's mother took her son home and covered him with ice borrowed from neighbors. These heroic acts were not isolated incidents. The relatives of the victims of the protests emerged on social media as focal points of reference, receiving a special degree of reverence and followership from the Iranian public. One could argue that the families of the victims, with their capacity to summon protests for the anniversaries and memorials of their loved ones, carried more authority over the protests' developments than the most well-known opposition figures, who had not yet successfully summoned a protest demonstration.

A week after Kian's death, the IR deployed security forces armed with live ammunition to the West Azerbaijan province and Kurdistan province to quell the ongoing strikes and protests in the Kurdish regions. Unbeknownst to the IR, despite closing the internet for the region prior to the attack, the utilization of Starlink internet distribution tools and internet access tools imported from abroad allowed Iranian Kurds to join live collaboration spaces and give live updates of the ongoing developments.

The disturbing sounds of live ammunition, explosions, and screams reverberated with the thousands of Iranians connected to these spaces. Broadcasting networks like Iran International provided live coverage of these developments for millions of other Iranians. During these episodes, the cities of Javanrud, Piranshahr, and Mahabad were essentially under the informal martial law of the IRGC.

Concurrently, during the days when the IRGC escalated its violence in these cities, the Qatar World Cup was also being watched by Iranians, who were divided on either supporting the players or celebrating their loss. While every major opposition figure at this time was writing solidarity messages for the Kurds, Pahlavi posted a picture of the Iranian football jersey with a Lion and Sun flag, asking the national team players to wear the correct jersey during their games.

This response was largely ridiculed by ethnic interest activists and heavily criticized by many who considered the discourse unfitting and negligent of the misery of the Kurdish people. This assumption reinforced the frame propagated by left-leaning opposition groups antagonistic to Pahlavi, portraying him as representing the same discriminatory institution against minorities as the IR.

By the fourteenth week of the continued protests, two significant events galvanized the solidarity discourse across the opposition once again. Firstly, an unprecedented terrorist chemical attack took place in an Iranian girls' school. The first suspected agencies behind this attack were the IRGC or its fanatically ideological branch of volunteers, the NOKHSA. The chemical attacks on schoolgirls continued weekly, sometimes with multiple cases on a single day, until the following year. When Alinejad called for a demonstration against these terrorist attacks, the largest participants were other schoolgirls who had become the new force of the united strata in the protest fold.

The second key event that took place during the same period was the execution of the first WLF protestor, Mohsen Shekari. Once again, reverting to Moaddel's thesis, the aggressive repression by the IR contributed more to the discursive patterns of the opposition than the strategic frame preferences of the opposition groups.

In the following week, another protestor, Majidreza Rahnavard, was also executed by the IR. A forced confession taken from Rahnavard, who was filmed with a broken arm, raised questions about the IR being the culprit behind his broken limb. The pictures on his Instagram later confirmed this. The arm that had been fractured, possibly under torture, bore the emblem of the Lion and Sun. From here on, Rahnavard emerged as a symbol of the protest movement that most strongly resonated with the political frame of Pahlavism.

After the execution of Majidreza, a concerning trend of frame alignment and expansion emerged, whereby different martyrs of the protests were appropriated by various opposition groups, each claiming the deceased as part of their faction. This phenomenon led to a competitive struggle for legitimacy, with opposition groups utilizing the profiles or preferences of the fallen or imprisoned protesters to assert their narrative as representative of the broader protest movement. Notably, this tactic was extensively employed by monarchist and ethnic interest factions.

On January 1, 2023, an initiative led by Karimi, involving clandestine negotiations among leading opposition figures, resulted in a synchronized social media post by key opposition figures advocating for unity, solidarity, and virtue in the collective resistance against the IR. This zenith of solidarity was further strengthened by national unity in response to the IR's execution of Mohammad Mehdi Karami and Mohammad Hosseini. The burgeoning sense of unity within the opposition, fueled by the ongoing chemical attacks on girls' schools and the execution of additional protesters, reignited fears of widespread executions reminiscent of the 1980s. This concern galvanized more nationwide demonstrations, notably orchestrated by the PS750 Association to commemorate the anniversary of the IRGC's downing of PS750.

In the aftermath of the initial chemical attacks on girls' schools, the discourse across Iranian social media platforms predominantly focused on advocating for the designation of the IRGC as a terrorist organization in the EU and the UK, aiming to curtail its financial operations. This campaign was significantly amplified by prominent opposition figures, particularly Alinejad. On January 15, a collective social media campaign emerged, echoing the call to list the IRGC as a terrorist organization. However, this unified stance experienced a schism, with the most conservative factions expressing reservations about listing the IRGC as a terrorist entity in the EU and the UK.

Amir Taheri, a notable senior journalist in exile and chief editor of the monarchist *Keyhan* London newspaper, protested the move to designate the IRGC as a terrorist organization, arguing it could pave the way for military intervention by foreign powers in Iran. He contended that such a process would weaken Iran's defensive capabilities more significantly than it would constrain the IR. This perspective was shared by several monarchist figures during debates on *Iran International*, notably Shahriar Ahy, a former chief advisor to Pahlavi.

This debate led to critics of Pahlavi suggesting he remains sympathetic to the IRGC, with some speculating that Pahlavi is counting on an IRGC coup d'état to oust Khamenei, rather than advocating for systemic regime change. This allegation is grounded in Pahlavi's consistent position to keep the opposition inclusive of those wishing to break away from the military complex and the crackdown apparatus of the IR. Time and time again, however, he has refused to elaborate on mechanisms and logistics for accommodating those deserting their positions. Instead, he diverts questions on this matter to the 'experts'.

By the 20th week of the protests, in-group consolidation discourse began to dominate over national solidarity, which then constituted only 24% of the discourse patterns in Iranian Telegram groups. In his *ManotoTV* interview, Pahlavi was questioned about his willingness to cooperate with all opposition

factions, including those favoring the ethnic balkanization of Iran. This question aimed to cluster Federalists, predominantly PDKI and Komala, along with openly secessionist groups.

Pahlavi outlined four minimal conditions for collaboration, one of which emphasized preserving territorial integrity. From a political science perspective, one might question whether Pahlavi genuinely misunderstands that territorial integrity depends on neighboring countries, not on ethnic interest groups advocating for a federal system. It seems Pahlavi's framework for future collaboration was strategically crafted to exclude groups like PDKI and Komala, with whom he had failed negotiations.

Furthermore, Pahlavi's assertion that his ability to represent the Iranian people internationally hinges on an evident desire by the public to delegate him this representation started a pivotal online mobilization. As one of the most recognizable opposition figures, Pahlavi has garnered substantial domestic support. His interview sparked two parallel campaigns: one on social media and another via a petition to validate public demand for his representation internationally. The social media campaign, named Vekalat, featured a hashtag translating to "I delegate"

During this period, national solidarity was compromised by in-group consolidation, with factions on the left, including confederalist parties advocating for federalism, criticizing the campaign as an attempt to dominate the opposition and disrupt established unity by selectively choosing who is to be represented. This division even spread to counterprotests with many joining the trend as "I don't delegate" on social media.

However, the individuals endorsing Pahlavi's representation were not exclusively Pahlavists or monarchists. His well-established profile and the perceived necessity of the campaign for successful negotiations that could intensify pressure on the IR garnered support across various social strata and political viewpoints. Concurrently, coercive discursive behavior from Pahlavist royalists surfaced, branding those who refrained from delegating as traitors, false opposition, controlled opposition, culprits of the 1979 revolution, separatists, and members of the "unholy alliance of the red and black." Notably, key opposition figures like Karimi, who had maintained distinct autonomy within the opposition, not only endorsed Pahlavi but also actively engaged others with the query "will you delegate?" Many political structures that emerged during the protest movement, such as 7Aban, Iran Novin, and other monarchist entities, also participated in this campaign.

This presented a stark illustration of in-group consolidation and out-group hostility being simultaneously employed to dominate the opposition narrative. Pahlavi has consistently portrayed himself not merely as a representative of monarchists, but striving over four decades to establish himself as a 'sovereign' entity above oppositional partisanship, supposedly supporting all active groups

irrespective of their stances. While he has positioned himself as nonpartisan, his social media endorsements are exclusively reciprocal to advocates of monarchy, with few exceptions. It's important to note that Pahlavi did not explicitly initiate either the campaign or the petition.

By the 21st week, the discourse of solidarity had significantly diminished in favor of in-group consolidation. Other prominent opposition figures remained unresponsive to the campaign despite its growing momentum. A week into the campaign's expansion, Pahlavi acknowledged it, affirming his readiness to represent the nation. Concurrently, leaked discussions from a Komala meeting indicated ongoing negotiations among figures like Alinejad, Pahlavi, Mohtadi, Esmailiun, Ebadi, Abbas Milani, and others, aiming to establish a Coalition Council. This was also confirmed in a later interview with Karim Sajjadpour, who hosted the Georgetown event. Sajjadpour recollects Alinejad was most adamant about the formation of the council, and all the members showed humility and mutual respect for one another throughout the formation of the council. This was also confirmed by interviews of Alinejad 9 months after the collapse of the coalition.

This council, envisaged to encompass the full spectrum of opposition, intended to centralize oppositional influence through internal consensus-building. The timing of Pahlavi's interview and the campaign may have appeared strategically designed to endow Pahlavi with the quantifiable political leverage necessary to cement his de facto leadership of the opposition. This observation however contradicted the testimonies of Sajjadpour whose interview posits Pahlavi's reluctance to be addressed as "His Highness" or any other formal monarchial title on the website of the council.

The discourse of solidarity experienced a resurgence in the following two weeks, reaching new heights as six key opposition figures announced a synchronous post regarding a forthcoming press conference at Georgetown University to discuss the future of democracy in Iran. The participants included Pahlavi, Alinjead, Karimi, Farahani, Ebadi, Mohtadi, Esmailiun, and Iranian-British actress Nazanin Boniadi. The event, held at Georgetown University's Institute for Women, Peace and Security (GIWPS) and titled 'The Future of Iran's Democracy Movement', took place on the eve of the 44th anniversary of the establishment of the IR. There, the most prominent Iranian activists united to pledge their commitment to establishing democracy in Iran, emphasizing the necessity of unity against the IR and asserting that the time was not right to debate the precise nature of a future democratic government in Iran.

The event was met with widespread approval across the political spectrum, signaling a shift towards a new discursive paradigm of functional oppositionality after four decades of discord in deliberation. Despite the general positive reception, two groups expressed opposition to the formation of the

council: the royalist monarchists, who decried Pahlavi for associating with “nobodies,” and the mainstream left organizations, along with confederalist groups, which had historically difficult dialogic efforts with monarchists.

Further complicating the political dynamics, leaked audio from Mohtadi revealed that the most virulent criticism of Komala during this period came not from its traditional adversaries, the far-right nationalists, but rather from PJAK and other Kurdish parties. These groups accused Mohtadi of treason for engaging in dialogue with “the son of a dictator.” Despite the PDKI’s long-standing communications with Pahlavi aimed at reaching compromises, they publicly maintained a stance of “no negotiation with the son of a dictator,” positioning themselves against Komala and Mohtadi in a seemingly trivial manner. This development marked a rare instance where groups from opposite ends of the political spectrum aligned in opposition to the formation of a Coalition Council that sought to represent a broader swath of the Iranian opposition. The direct impact of these discursive actions on the movement’s trajectory is a subject for future academic inquiry.

The day following the Georgetown conference, key opposition figures called for another large-scale demonstration akin to those held in Berlin, this time across the U.S. The events in Washington D.C. and California reportedly attracted over 80,000 supporters. Another demonstration took place in Iran, marking the anniversary of the revolution. The turnouts, as expected, were minuscule compared to the demonstrations of the diaspora.

Yet, the demonstrations varied in ethos. In the Orange County and Los Angeles areas, strongholds of exiled Iranian monarchists, the political identity of the demonstrators was clearly reflected in the chants and slogans. During Pahlavi’s speech in California, he promoted the slogan “Woman, Life, Freedom,” but the crowd responded with monarchist slogans, including “long live the King.” Pahlavi’s political maneuvers to distance himself from the sectarian and undemocratic virtues of his royalist supporters would, to no avail, change throughout his engagement with the opposition.

Monarchist attendees also revived a contentious slogan endorsed by Yasmine Pahlavi: “Death to three corrupts: Mullahs, Leftists, Mojaheds.” Despite the emerging unity, factions within the opposition aimed to undermine the diverse representation in the council. For instance, when Alinejad met with French President Macron on February 13th, she faced criticism from the monarchists who accused her of misrepresenting Iranians and the movement and presenting the national revolution as a feminist movement centered on hijab issues—none of which were warranted. To this day, the events Alinejad is invited to as a speaker are bombarded with Monarchists contacting the event organizers to plead with

them to revoke Alinejad's invitation. This would repeat at the Copenhagen Democracy Summit 2024 and Munich Security Conference.

Following the Georgetown event, opposition members engaged with foreign dignitaries, culminating in an invitation to the Munich Security Conference, representing Iranian opposition instead of the IR. The conference on February 18 paralleled domestic shifts, with workplace protests, strikes, and educational demonstrations gaining momentum in Iran amid rising concerns over chemical attacks on girls' schools. According to Sajjadpour, prior to the Coalition Council, hardly any foreign secretaries would agree to meet with Pahlavi, given skepticism from left-leaning groups about promoting undemocratic right-wing populism and violent reprisals from the IR, such as attacking consulates or embassies of European countries in Tehran. Sajjadpour argued that it was through the council that Pahlavi was invited to partake as a representative of Iranians. This matter entirely contradicted the frame narrative of the royalists, who pandered to the impression that the members of the council were merely using Pahlavi and his name to receive recognition from foreign diplomats.

In London, a lesser-known Iranian opposition figure, Vahid Beheshti, initiated a wet hunger strike outside the Foreign Office, demanding the UK government designate the IRGC as a terrorist entity. Concurrently, a call for demonstrations on February 20 in Brussels, envisioned as a sequel to the Berlin event, highlighted ongoing unity efforts among opposition groups.

The organization and sponsorship of the Brussels event were mired in ambiguity, with claims of involvement from both the controversial Farashgard Foundation and 7Aban's spokesperson Bashirtash, alongside Swedish-Iranian MP, Alireza Akhundi, and other European MPs advocating for the designation of the IRGC as a terrorist organization.

In the aftermath of the Berlin demonstration, those Iranians harboring resentment over the Lion and Sun flag's contested display opted either to sanction the Brussels event or to remain in Munich to support Pahlavi's extended presence for the Munich Security Conference.

At the Brussels event, flags became potent symbols of identity and belief within the diverse opposition. Those carrying the civil flag of Iran or flags with the Kufic inscription of "WLF" typically aligned with leftist ideologies. In contrast, the blue heraldic flag of the Pahlavi family, the crowned Lion and Sun, and placards of the royal family signified right-wing affiliations. The nuanced positions of those carrying the crownless Lion and Sun flag or the purple Kaviani flag, which symbolizes the myth of Kaveh as an Iranian hero for liberation, represented a blend of left and right sentiments. Surprisingly, the demonstration also saw a significant presence of flags from ethnic confederalist and separatist groups, including the Azerbaijani confederalist and separatist organization GAMOH, the Al-Ahwaz

group, and the separatist flag of Balochistan, eliciting outrage from nationalist factions. The Kurdish flag, once contentious, was more readily accepted due to its association with the protest's focal points and its pan-Iranian colors.

During Alinejad's speeches, monarchist chants of “Long live the King” clashed with a larger group using whistles and cheers to drown them out. A separate podium for monarchists featured Hamed Fard, a former IR propagandist musician recently praised by Pahlavi. Fard's speech, questioning Esmailiun's past absences and bolstering Pahlavi as the opposition's de facto leader, resonated with the monarchist audience, despite Pahlavi's stance against being recognized as the coalition's leader. Fard's position was neither novel nor original. Since November, many royalists contended that any figure that does not pledge to Pahlavi is competing with him.

The Brussels demonstration showcased a rivalry among legacy opposition figures, each vying for dominance and group identity, a sentiment echoed in speeches promoting unity and warning against the IR's divisive tactics. The subsequent release of the Coalition Council's charter sparked mixed reactions, with monarchists particularly disillusioned by the contrasting treatment of flags at different demonstrations, a topic that remained hotly debated in monarchist circles until the Coalition Council's eventual disintegration.

Before delving deeper into the discursive events leading to the charter's formation and its aftermath, it is essential to contextualize the background of the key actors involved, which the following section aims to address.

7.2. Leadership Contest

In the evolving discourse, the de facto leadership of the opposition was perceived by their respective supporter bases to be divided between Alinejad, Esmailiun, and Pahlavi. Pahlavi's supporters leveraged the legacy of the Pahlavi dynasty, the results of the Vekalat campaign, and his four decades of consistent rhetoric to position him as the hegemon and the de facto leader of the opposition. Conversely, the republicans, feminists, and national federalists, who rejected the ethnic confederalism of groups like PDKI and Komala and royalists' coercion to monarchism, gravitated towards Alinejad and Esmailiun.

While neither Alinejad nor Esmailiun explicitly declared their political stances post-critical juncture, their perceived opposition to royalist values and openness to leftist and feminist discourses positioned them as representatives of the 'Others' who lacked representation under the establishing blocs. Their willingness to engage with politically marginalized groups further distinguished them from the normative political narratives.

All three figures eschewed the notion of single-person leadership, advocating for system-oriented leadership and council-based governance to guide the protest movements. However, the discourse of oppositionality remained fixated on these individuals rather than the collective representation of a Coalition Council, exacerbated by the intensifying in-group consolidation challenging the council's leadership.

Detractors of Pahlavi leveraged the royalists' maneuvers to hegemonize the discourse, monopolize oppositionality, and consolidate power as evidence of anti-democratic and authoritarian tendencies of Pahlavism, leading to mutual accusations of "false opposition" and deepening rifts between the two blocs within public and digital spaces.

S.Razavi's essay "Discord in the Diaspora: Agonism in the Woman, Life, Freedom Movement for Democracy" (2023) examines the emergence of agonism from consensus deliberation, arguing for the productive potential of political conflict.¹⁷² Contrary to the conventional view that advocates for compromise and views conflict as detrimental, Razavi emphasizes that agonism is not only inevitable but essential for democracy, fostering a space for engaging with contentious ideas and building robust democratic institutions. She urges embracing conflict in dialogues, even when they are fraught with tension, to enhance democratic engagement.

¹⁷² Razavi, Sahar. "Discord in the Diaspora: Agonism in the Woman, Life, Freedom Movement for Democracy." *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 55, no. 4 (2023): 754–58. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020743823001435>.

Razavi further observes a rise in hostilities within the US-based Iranian diaspora, suggesting the presence of strong antidemocratic currents within some segments of the Iranian American community.

For Esmailiun and Alinejad, their distinct personalities were starkly evident. Alinejad's confrontational style and rhetoric led her critics, particularly monarchists, to label her as a populist demagogue, accusing her of exploiting the Pahlavi identity for personal advancement. These accusations referenced her past as a journalist in Iran and her previous marriage to an Iranian MP, which was claimed to facilitate her journalistic access to elite political circles. Additionally, Alinejad's role in the White Wednesdays campaigns was criticized for allegedly compromising her followers' safety, though many of these accusations aligned with narratives propagated by the IR. The rapid spread of such rumors and allegations on social media platforms, where authentic information often struggles to prevail, exacerbated divisions within the opposition.

Alinejad faced multiple assassination attempts by the IR, given her prominent role in pressuring the regime. Her association with early hijab protests and the subsequent WLF movement established her as a significant figure in the eyes of many foreign dignitaries. Alinejad was also the most vocal proponent of forming a Coalition Council among key opposition figures before its actual inception, highlighting her commitment to collective opposition efforts.

Esmailiun faced criticism for his reluctance to collaborate with Pahlavi, allegations of antisemitism, and his past interactions and comments related to Yasser Arafat, which were used to brand him as a reformist and controlled opposition, linking him to the 1979 revolution's legacy. Conversely, Esmailiun's supporters highlighted his achievements with the PS750 Association and his role in organizing major demonstrations, contrasting these successes with Pahlavi's perceived failures and indecisiveness. Pahlavi's initiatives, including the claim that the mechanism for operationalizing strike funds was nearly completed, were heavily scrutinized by his detractors. An important note must also be added here: The stark dualism adopted by the royalist discourse disallows the proponents of monarchy and supporters of Pahlavi to criticize the crown prince. Those who initiate a debate on criticizing Pahlavi are ostracized, harassed, intimidated, and if they were previously endorsed by Pahlavi, they will get 'unfollowed' on his social media.

The intensity of attacks against these three key opposition figures starkly contrasted with the leadership qualities they purported to embody. Each struggled to manage the narrative or accept responsibility for the divisive discourse proliferating among their followers, demonstrating the complex dynamics and challenges within the opposition's leadership and its base.

7.4. Mahsa Charter

By March 10, the Mahsa Charter was officially released, earning accolades for its fulfillment after delays from its initially promised date in late February. The charter's logo featured a logogram of a fist forming the Persian word for "Woman," set against a minimalist backdrop of white with black text, and accented with ribbons in the colors of the Iranian flag. Notably absent were any nationalist symbols such as the Lion and Sun, crowns, or maps of Iran, marking a departure from the traditional imagery prevalent in previous coalition efforts.

Content-wise, the charter bore resemblance to the ITC's charter and the Oath of Cooperation signed by parties like the Mashruteh, Tasmin, and ITC. Leaked audio from Komala indicated that the charter's inception was led by Milani, Alinejad, and Mohtadi, with Mohtadi expressing concerns that the charter's initial language could alienate left-leaning organizations and hinder dialogic consensus. This was contradicted by an interview with Sajjadpour, who argued that Esmailiun had created the first draft with the assistance of activists within Iran. He noted his efforts to exclude nationalist rhetoric to maintain potential inclusivity for groups like the PDKI and socialist republican parties representing Arab and Baloch communities. Sajjadpour, however, argued the content was criticized by many prior to its publication and an alternative draft of it was also generated. Only one member of the council showed restraint in publishing the charter, while the other members contended to release it given the months of delay it had for its publishing.

The charter's signatories reportedly took an oath of confidentiality regarding its content, a claim contradicted by Hossein Ronaghi in an X space discussion, where he asserted his involvement in consulting on the charter's content. Ronaghi highlighted the influence of Mehdi Hajati, a former reformist with alleged ties to the IR, sparking controversy over the charter's integrity and potential undermining.

Critiques of the charter varied: nationalists lamented the absence of distinctly Iranian elements and contested the replacement of "territorial integrity" with "national unity." The charter's feminist and potentially leftist undertones drew suspicion, with accusations that it aimed to steer the protest movement towards a feminist-communist-Islamist revolution. Alireza Kiani of the INP critiqued the charter's democratic credentials, arguing that the stipulation for all officials to be elected could preclude monarchical options in a free referendum as undemocratic, despite Pahlavi's preference for a republican system over hereditary monarchy.

From the perspective of the legacy left organizations, the charter was faulted for not explicitly precluding monarchism, while ethnic-interest groups criticized its failure to acknowledge Iran's multinationality, fearing it might perpetuate exclusionary practices. Rumors circulated suggesting Mohtadi was coerced into collaboration, casting a shadow over the charter's unifying intentions. These diverse reactions underscored the complex interplay of political ideologies and aspirations within the Iranian opposition, reflecting the challenging task of articulating a collective vision for Iran's future.

7.5. Iranian Intermezzo

The term "Iranian Intermezzo" traditionally refers to the historical period that witnessed the rise and fall of various indigenous Iranian dynasties on the Iranian Plateau following the 7th-century Muslim conquest of Iran. This title can aptly describe the tumultuous phase following the abandonment of the Mahsa Charter, encapsulating the transient unity and subsequent fragmentation among the signatories.

In a March 2024 interview, Alinejad disclosed that the formation of the Coalition Council was primarily a strategic move to facilitate meetings with foreign diplomats and to enhance external pressure on Iran. Following the charter's release, its representatives were actively engaged in delivering speeches, conducting press conferences, and engaging in high-level diplomatic dialogues to bolster support for the WLF movement.

By March 15, 27 weeks into the protests, the situation in Iran had significantly escalated, with reports of approximately 60,000 arrests and over a hundred individuals facing execution risks. Protest activities had evolved to include industry-specific strikes, financial withdrawals, cash-only transactions, traffic disruptions, and acts of civil disobedience such as eschewing the hijab and disseminating slogans nationwide. Persistent Friday prayers in Balochistan showcased ongoing protest momentum, featuring placards expressing solidarity with the revolutionary cause. Escalating chemical attacks on girls' schools also intensified the demonstrations led by teachers and students.

The prevailing discourse during this period emphasized national solidarity, focusing on supporting workers and prisoners. Critics of the charter, who feared it might lead to the balkanization of Iran or reinforce a fascistic monarchy, were often discredited, with such narratives also being promoted by the IR to sow further discord.

Amidst these developments, rumors of internal strife and potential disintegration of the coalition surfaced, particularly around the Tirgan conference in Toronto. Speculations abounded regarding the stability of the council and Pahlavi's continued involvement, with such rumors even echoed by individuals close to Pahlavi.

The Tirgan conference served as a platform for addressing critiques of the charter, with assurances of pending amendments based on public feedback. Pahlavi's analogy of the Coalition Council as a bus with open doors highlighted the ongoing discussions about expanding membership to ensure a more comprehensive and representative coalition, echoing Alinejad's commitment to inclusivity and broader representation within the opposition's ranks.

In the ensuing weeks, criticism from royalists intensified. Manoto hosted podcasts that propagated rumors, suggesting the council was excluding monarchist members, advocating for Iran's balkanization, undermining Persian heritage, and associating with the 1979 revolution. These attacks were predominantly concentrated on the X platform, with even Pahlavi's close advisors turning against the coalition, accusing it of monopolizing the opposition and controlling the revolutionary narrative. This shift led to a dominant discourse of hostility, overshadowing previous solidarity efforts.

On April 4, Pahlavi suggested incorporating senior members from the ITC, Tasmim, and Mashruteh into the coalition, announcing this on his social media. Alinejad and Nazanin Boniadi began the process of evaluating these candidates for inclusion. However, rumors quickly resurfaced, fueled by Manoto, claiming that all proposed members were rejected, exacerbating tensions within the opposition.

According to Alinejad, women in the group, especially Boniadi, faced harassment, likened to the vetting practices of the IR's Guardianship Council, with criticisms often being sexist and misogynistic. Pahlavi's subsequent recommendations to add individuals like Kalashi and hip hop artist Shahin Najafi, who had been politically vocal on YouTube, intensified the rumors driven by Manoto.

Despite not outright rejecting these potential members and expressing willingness to discuss their inclusion, Pahlavi prematurely announced on social media that efforts to integrate new members had failed. This led to a sustained period of out-group hostility dominating the discourse.

By the 31st week, around April 15, Boniadi deactivated her social media accounts due to escalating harassment from monarchists. Shortly thereafter, Mohtadi denounced the monarchist attacks as undemocratic, asserting that such pressures would not deter the group's mission. Concurrently, Pahlavi announced a trip to Israel, invited by the Israeli government and its intelligence ministry, where he was presented as the leader of the opposition, accompanied by his wife and close advisors. This development further inflamed the already volatile dynamics within the opposition. None of the coalition members reacted to Pahlavi's unexpected visit to Israel.

Leaked audio from Mohtadi's July meeting and Alinejad's interview with Iran International nine months later revealed that Pahlavi exited the Coalition Council before his announced trip to Israel, with Foad Pashai, leader of the Mashruteh party, indicating that Pahlavi's departure was due to perceived disrespect towards his wife—allegedly by Alinejad. This development wasn't publicized until several months after the council's dissolution.

Following Pahlavi's disclosure of his Israel trip, Esmailiun publicly exited the coalition, attributing his departure to Pahlavi's undemocratic actions. Subsequently, Pahlavi ceased following all coalition signatories except Mohtadi. Alinejad, appearing on Iran International, apologized to the public for the unfolding events and disclosed Pahlavi's formal exit from the council, attributing the pressures to unfounded rumors spread by Manoto about the non-inclusion of new members.

Concurrently, Beheshti's call for a demonstration in London to label the IRGC as a terrorist entity saw backing from Esmailiun. However, figures supported by Pahlavi launched attacks against the London demonstration participants. Pahlavi's eldest daughter initially endorsed, then retracted her support for the event. Beheshti faced accusations of deceit regarding his hunger strike, not just from anonymous sources but also from individuals like Vahid Ranjbari, a staunch royalist monarchist, who also targeted Alinejad and Esmailiun with defamatory claims.

The London event failed to attract the same level of participation as previous demonstrations in Brussels and Berlin. Interestingly, Yasmine Pahlavi attended a concurrent event in another city. Monarchists boycotting the London demonstration, alleging Esmailiun's false accusations against Pahlavi, showed their support at the Israeli embassy in London, aligning with the Israeli officials' warm reception of Pahlavi. This gathering, however, was modest, drawing fewer than 100 attendees over four hours.

Ali Javanmardi, host of AVAToday and a PDKI member, released a video titled "Footstep Creeps of Fascism," advocating for severing any coalition or consensus-building endeavors with Pahlavi and his supporters, highlighting a deepening rift within the opposition. Amidst increasing scrutiny from Iran International on the coalition's breakdown, monarchist factions initiated a failed boycott of the network. Etemadi, an advisor to Pahlavi, leveraged his Farashgard tactics to denigrate critics as collaborators with the IR, labeling Iran International's journalists as terrorists masquerading as media personnel, despite the network's London office closure due to terror threats advised by the Metropolitan Police.

As the 36th week of protests approached, the opposition's discourse in the diaspora, marred by internal conflicts, increasingly disconnected from the on-ground realities in Iran. In an effort to realign focus on Iranian affairs, the independent media group 1500Tasvir, alongside Esmailiun, launched the "We are together" campaign. However, the solidarity it aimed to foster was undermined by the divisive actions of Pahlavi's followers, who countered with a "We are with King" campaign.

On June 16, Pahlavi and various celebrities launched a unified call for political unity, aligning with Rahnavard's birthday leading to Mahsa's memorial in September, aiming to bolster strike efforts and

prepare for renewed protests. Despite broad approval, the initiative mainly resulted in monarchist-led gatherings on September 16, where inclusivity was overshadowed by harassment of non-monarchist attendees and ideological dominance in speeches.

In a separate incident on June 24, Art University students in Tehran explicitly rejected any dialogue with the IR, emphasizing the irreversible divide through a “No” campaign, which garnered widespread support across various political factions as the 40th week of protests neared. This campaign symbolized a fleeting moment of unity before dissolving into the political fray.

Contrastingly, Pahlavi’s endorsement of the “No” campaign did not prevent a segment of royalists from initiating a “Yes to Monarchy” movement, illustrating the persistent ideological fragmentation and the challenge of maintaining a cohesive opposition narrative as the protest anniversary approached.

Since the disintegration of the Coalition Council, communication among its former members ceased, exacerbating frustrations within the Iranian public. Aggressive in-group consolidation and hostile out-group dynamics, coupled with a lack of progress, led to widespread dissatisfaction. This discontent prompted a campaign titled “I take back my delegation,” reflecting disillusionment with the Vekalat campaign's unmet promises. The campaign, though mocked by revivalists, resonated enough to prompt Yasmin Pahlavi to withdraw from social media amidst the escalating acrimony.

The disunity within the opposition, especially among prominent figures, mirrors broader fractures within the diaspora. Inside Iran, various forms of opposition persist, while Iranians abroad have turned to platforms like Telegram and WhatsApp to support the uprising, continuing the discourse through social media. However, these channels are often plagued by distrust, division, and discord, leading to a decline in group cohesion as members exit the increasingly toxic and partisan environments. The opposition’s discord has led to disruptions reminiscent of the 1980s and 1990s in Iran, where Hezbollahi regime loyalists disrupted events not aligning with Islamic principles. Similar tactics emerge in the diaspora, with discursive spaces becoming targets of coordinated harassment campaigns.

Discursive analysis reveals a shift towards in-group consolidation post-council collapse, with solidarity resurfacing only in response to significant events in Iran. An example is the case of Armita Garavand, a Kurdish girl attacked by Iran's morality police, which reignited solidarity discourse 55 weeks into the protests. However, the opposition's response to Armita’s plight was limited to expressions of condolence and threats of retribution, highlighting a persistent gap between discourse and decisive action.

7.6. Dead-end Opposition

The WLF movement continues to manifest in Iran through acts of civil disobedience, such as hijab noncompliance and slogan writing, signaling persistent public dissatisfaction and a collective call for regime change. The mass boycott of the parliamentary elections in February further confirmed the public's ongoing discontent. However, the legacy opposition, which has dominated the narrative for the past four decades, is losing traction and relevance, with the notable exception of those deeply entrenched in royalism.

New talks of coalition building between IR reformists and monarchists emerged in May 2024, following a BBC interview with Mohammad Nasiri, editor-in-chief of a publication under the IR. Nasiri's suggestion that the opposition should focus on closing the gaps between Tajzadeh, a prominent reformist, and Shahzadeh (Pahlavi) has initiated a new discourse on future coalition-building projects. In a conference with UK-based activists, Pahlavi responded to the initiative by welcoming it and using the 'far-right' and 'far-left' extremists as scapegoats of the last failed coalition. This was ridiculed by the discourse on Iranian social media, referencing his wife's call for the execution of leftists, his advisors' accusation of journalists as terrorists, promotion of national socialism, threatening their detractors with violent nationalism, and labeling the WLF as a "cult of madness" as "mediator-right."

The analysis by Moaddel and Steinberg suggests that the failure to engage in effective discourse and build deliberative consensus typically results in the fading of certain narratives or the dominance of a single perspective. The persistent boycotts and denials of legitimacy between the left and right factions, aimed at monopolizing the definition of opposition, reveal a stark reality: none possess the substantial support needed to effectuate meaningful change, especially when employing exclusionary tactics that hinder cooperation.

Women, Life, Freedom was an apocalypse in its etymological sense—for the opposition and the Islamic Republic. It was a set of revelations that unfolded on many ends. It demonstrated that the prematurely conceived coalition of the opposition with veteran and popular key actors has not yet created a mechanism in four decades to consolidate democratic deliberation and consensus building. It also demonstrated that the IR is not willing to repeat the mistakes of the Pahlavi government and offer compromises to pacify the protesters. In the failure of dialogue, violence follows. The burden of potential violence emerging in response to the next wave of protests—given the unstable state the IR is in—falls on the opposition that failed to consolidate itself.

Reverting to the fourth theory that there is deliberation in the failure of the opposition, the findings suggest otherwise. The political culture, premature development of discourse, and responses of the IR to the protest movement contribute significantly to the failure of the coalition. What is evident from studying the discourse and episodic assessment of the movement is the general lack of deliberation in all aspects. The opposition has repeatedly failed to strategize a mechanism of success, and its lack of transparency further fuels speculative assumptions on the causes and mechanisms of failure.

Alternatively, Occam's razor offers a disappointing response to the question of where the discourse of coalition for 'Woman, Life, Freedom' failed. It simply points to an undisclosed argument between Alinejad and Yasmine Pahlavi which provoked Pahlavi's departure from the council.

Lastly, the possibility that the IR's counter-intelligence could orchestrate discord within opposition ranks cannot be dismissed, considering that many actions and narratives from the revivalist camp starkly contradict Pahlavi's avowed principles. This subject, as a contemporary and ongoing debate, must remain open for further scholarly analysis.

8. Conclusion

Revisiting the initial theory of this research, it was hypothesized that the legacy opposition prefers to maintain the status quo and hostility to dominate the opposition narrative. While this notion appears logical, it overlooks the nuanced individual characteristics that influence decision-making processes. The episodic discursive analysis reveals inconsistencies and illogical patterns in actions and discourse.

Efforts to dominate the opposition narrative through specific frames and to project politically charged agendas as universal solidarity were indeed observed. However, the long-term outcomes and the episodic evolution of these efforts lack a coherent strategic rationale. The discursive shifts leading to fragmentation are more aptly explained by competitive frame expansion among Pahlavi's supporters and counter-expansions by his critics, led by figures like Alinejad and Esmailiun. This dynamic positions the WLF protest as possessing a distinct narrative framework, shaped and modified by the events in Iran, reflecting the actions of protesters and the IR's responses. The solidarity discourse seems to be inherently tied to the domestic context of Iran, while the diaspora's opposition narrative is marked by in-group consolidation and out-group hostility, largely external to the country's immediate political landscape.

The fragmentation of the opposition may thus be attributed more to the unrealistic and grandiose perceptions of the exiled legacy opposition than to a calculated strategic preference. A more straightforward explanation might attribute the disintegration to the contrasting personalities within the opposition: Pahlavi's indecisiveness, Alinejad's ambition, and Esmailiun's ideological steadfastness, each contributing to the opposition's collective inefficacy.

The emergence of solidarity discourse is linked to critical junctures that resonate deeply with the public, gaining further momentum when opposition groups announce collaborative efforts. However, the impact of such opposition groups' discursive projections on the movement remains limited during active protest phases in Iran. The competitive frame expansion and internal disputes among legacy opposition factions tend to have a negligible effect on the ground, unless they align with a dominant, hegemonic frame.

The collapse of the Coalition Council exemplifies how significant attention and perceived importance can exacerbate the fragmentation of the opposition. This suggests that hegemonic frames, rather than those built on consensus, tend to be more unstable and prone to collapse under their own weight, akin to an overinflated bubble.

The emergence of celebrity politics and reliance on person-centric movements, as opposed to systemic ones, places disproportionate influence in the hands of a few individuals, potentially destabilizing the entire opposition effort. The legacy opposition's declining frame relevance, coupled with its inability to achieve significant outcomes or foster consensus, inadvertently supports the status quo of the IR.

The predicament facing the Iranian opposition points towards the necessity for a shift towards deliberative democracy and consensus-building. Such an approach could provide a more stable and inclusive platform for challenging the IR's rule. As long as legacy opposition groups remain fragmented and ineffective, the IR's sovereignty remains unchallenged – despite its unpredictable and unstable condition. This analysis could serve as a guide for both opposition groups seeking to refine their strategies and incumbent governments monitoring these dynamics.

While the WLF movement remains active to the date of writing this paragraph, it begs the inquiry of scholars of political science to inspect the continued development of Iran's most seminal critical juncture in the last four decades. The discussion on the subjects of the WLF movement as well as the discursive method remain open for academic inspection.

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